

D5.2 – Influence Factor Analysis

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Public report with the findings of the investigation on the role of ICT-related and transport-related influence factors on Value of Travel Time.

D.5.2 is associated to the MoTiV Task 5.4 described below.

Description of Task 5.4 “Influence Factor Analysis”

Task 5.4 Influence Factors Analysis (UNIZA): this task will assess the self-declared obstacles and promoters of the respective behaviour.

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About MoTiV

The Horizon 2020 project MoTiV (Mobility and Time Value) addresses the emerging perspectives on changing Value of Travel Time (VTT). Accordingly, it explores the dynamics of individual preferences, behaviours and lifestyles that influence travel and mobility choices. In other words, what does value of travel time mean for the end users, in relation to their travel experience?

The MoTiV project addresses VTT from the perspective of a single individual with a unique combination of personality, preferences, needs and expectations, in contrast with the traditional viewpoint of the economic dimension (time and cost savings). Its approach aims at achieving a broader and more interdisciplinary conceptualisation and understanding of VTT emphasising its “behavioural” component.

The main goal of the MoTiV project is to contribute to advancing research on VTT by introducing a conceptual framework for the estimation of VTT at an individual level, based on the value proposition of mobility. The conceptual framework will be validated through data collection and evaluation in at least 8 EU countries. The mobility and behavioural dataset will be collected using a mobile application developed by the project consortium, which will combine and integrate in an innovative way features from a multi-modal “journey planner” and an “activity/mobility diary”. With this mobile app, end-users will be able to more easily track, understand, and re-evaluate travel decisions to make the most of their free time in accordance with personal preferences, lifestyle, interests, and budget. The target is to engage in the data collection process a minimum of 4.000 participants actively using the MoTiV app for at least two weeks. Besides validating the conceptual framework, the dataset will be made available to the scientific community as an Open Dataset to stimulate further research in this area.

The MoTiV project findings will produce scientific and policy outcomes, as well as potential business developments, including the development of new mobility services and the extension of existing applications, such as the ones offered by the business partners of the Consortium (i.e. *routeRANK journey planner*¹ and the *PiggyBaggy*² app for crowdsourced deliveries).

Partners

¹ <https://www.routerank.com>

² <http://piggybaggy.com>

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
DCC	Data Collection Campaign
E	Enjoyment
F	Fitness
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IFA	Influence Factor Analysis
IT	Internet Technology
MoTiV	Mobility and Time Value
P	Productivity
PT	Public Transport
Q&A	Questions & Answers
RD	Road Directness
RQ	Road Quality
RS	Road Smoothness
U.S.	United States
VOT	Value of Time
VS	Vehicle Smoothness
VTT	Value of Travel Time
WI	Worthwhileness Index

MoTiV Consortium Partners and Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
UNIZA	University of Žilina
CoRe	CoReorient Oy
ECF	European Cyclists' Federation ASBL
EUT	Fundació Eurecat
INESC ID	Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores, Investigação e Desenvolvimento em Lisboa
routeRANK	routeRANK Ltd
TIS	Consultores em Transportes Inovação e Sistemas S.A.

Executive summary

Unlike traditional transport economics claims, the perception of the value of travel time is not only influenced by travel time and cost savings, which are currently considered to be the primary contributors to the value of travel time. Depending on the situation, other factors such as increased comfort or well-being may influence a traveller's perceived value of travel time as much as or more than time and cost. To reveal the potential influence of factors on the perception of the travel time value, an Influence Factor Analysis was performed for three chosen areas, as described in the Grant Agreement:

- **Weather:** to understand the direct impact of weather conditions on people's travel behaviour;
- **Information and Communications Technology (ICT):** to identify whether the use of ICT and the possibility of multitasking has an effect on the worthwhileness of travel time, and;
- **Transport infrastructure and services:** to reveal the impact of the quality of transport infrastructure and services on the perceived experience and satisfaction regarding travel time.

Inputs for the influence factor analysis were gathered via Woorti app, a dedicated mobile application developed in the frame of the MoTiV project. The dataset consists of multimodal data gathered in at least 8 different European countries, thanks to the contributions of almost 3,400 active users, between the months of May and December 2019. The sample is considered to be robust and suitable for a comprehensive analysis, allowing the research team to gain an understanding of traveller's reasons for her travel choices and identify factors influencing behavioural mobility patterns, data regarding trip origin/destination, travel time, travel distance, modes of transport, as well as traveller's contextual assessment of worthwhile travel time, details on the type of value of time (e.g. productivity, enjoyment, fitness) and activities carried out during the trip. For the sake of data processing and analysis, Python was used for estimating the effects of the introduced variables.

The report addresses 18 research questions related to weather, ICT, and transport infrastructure and services investigating the impact of different variables on mobility choices and assessing the value of travel time. These questions were also examined across attributes such as gender, country, trip purpose, and other socio-economic variables where relevant.

Results indicate that some of the factors in the three analysed areas represent important elements influencing the travel behaviour and the perception of travel time worthwhileness. Data analysis showed that for all trip legs where experience factors were selected by users, the majority was referred to experience factors having a positive influence on the quality of travel time representing around 79% of the total responses. The **weather** is considered to be one of the factors that has a great impact on the choice of mode of transport. It was found that weather was among the most frequent experience factors in almost all transport mode categories. However, based on the analysis of trip legs in the Walking category, a negative experience with weather does not seem to affect the worthwhileness of a trip.

The impact of **ICT** on travel behaviour and the associated value of travel time was analysed in terms of ICT activities and the experience factors related to ICT. In general, people tend to listen to audio and browse the Internet while travelling. Considering modes of transport, listening was the most frequently performed activity in the case of walking, cycling and emerging micromobility options, whilst browsing the Internet was the most important ICT activity for those who used private motorised and public transport modes. Regarding worthwhileness evaluation, people reading electronic devices while travelling evaluate their travel time as the most worthwhile. A significant difference was

identified in the evaluation by gender. Men who read electronic devices or browsed the Internet rated travel time as more worthwhile than women. On the other hand, women considered their travel time more worthwhile than men when they watched video or movies. The difference between men and women was also identified in the perception of the worthwhileness and importance of Internet connectivity as an experience factor. Men who chose Internet connectivity as an important factor while travelling consider their travel time more worthwhile than women. Regarding different modes of transport, Internet connectivity was identified as an important experience factor for travelling and positively rated by long-distance public transport users.

In the part focused on **transport infrastructure and services**, positive and negative experience factors and their correlation with mood and worthwhileness ratings were analysed. Among the top experience factors that positively influence the perception of travel time are “Simplicity of the route” and “Reliability of travel time”. The analysis also demonstrated that approximately 40% of the trip legs where reliability had a positive impact were given the best evaluation in terms of worthwhileness. On the other hand, among the most frequent negative experience factors are “Noise level”, “Air Quality” and “Cars and other vehicles”. Many uncommon experience factors, compared to conventional planning, rated high in both negative and positive evaluations of perceived value of travel time such as “Ability to do what I wanted”, “Scenery” or “Other people”. It was also revealed that travellers give more importance to the factor “Crowdedness_Seating” for long distance public transport trips. The worthwhileness of travel time is also affected by factors related to smoothness, which significantly affect some of the activities performed during travel.

When filtering trip legs by alternative modes performed by users of private motorised modes, the importance of experience factors is quite different to the average trend. These findings can provide insights towards which are the areas of improvement that can lead to increased levels of satisfaction for trips within Cycling & Emerging Micromobility and Public Transport Short Distance, potentially shifting car drivers travel behaviour.

The concept of worthwhileness is complex with many variables and different interrelations among them. Considering the multi-dimensionality of worthwhile or wasted travel time as perceived by travellers, it is challenging to identify and demonstrate the importance of factors influencing this perception with confidence. The complexity of this concept requires a more detailed analysis and data modelling which can potentially identify additional correlations. The forthcoming publications within the scope of MoTiV project and planned deliverables will shed light to additional results.

1. Introduction

This section presents the context and scope of the report, together with a summary of the structure of this deliverable.

1.1 Context and scope

This report forms Deliverable 5.2 which is part of Work Package 5 on Evaluation, describing the results and implications emerged with the analysis of the MoTiV dataset. This deliverable is the outcome of Task 5.4 regarding Influence Factors Analysis which assesses the self-declared obstacles and drivers of the respective travel behaviour. This public report presents the findings of the investigation on the role of weather conditions, ICT-related and transport infrastructure-related influence factors on Value of Travel Time.

Deliverable 5.2 primarily serves MoTiV Objective 3 which addresses the need to assess to what extent ICT connectivity and transport services/infrastructure affect VTT across leisure and work activities and within cultures and generations. In particular, this study is in alignment with specific objectives 3.1 and 3.2 of the MoTiV project:

- Specific Objective 3.1: cross-cultural, generational and gender analysis of **ICT-related influence factors in travel option choice (including purpose, mode and route choice), relevant activities carried out in relation to the travel (travel preparation, while travelling and at destination)** and overall impact on VTT. The analysis will not only consider the benefits of using ICT to carry out meaningful activities while on the move, particularly via smartphones and tablets, but also their negative impact on the perception of travel time. The analysis will evaluate in which contexts and situations ICT is expected to reduce or increase perceived VTT.
- Specific Objective 3.2: cross-cultural, generational and gender analysis of **influence factors linked to the transportation system and supporting infrastructure**. This includes, among others, advanced transport connections, frequency of connections, available seat places, availability of shared mobility facilities, bicycle lanes. The analysis will evaluate in which contexts and situations factors linked to the transportation system and supporting infrastructure are expected to reduce or increase perceived VTT.

The influence factor analysis presented in this report is also connected to Expected Impact 2 of the MoTiV project which aims to identify influence factors affecting specific transport mode choices and impacting travel time value perception in the context of life style and personal values which can be a basis for transport policies and strategies. As results will be quantified this might become an additional basis for policy measures to affect the boundary conditions towards a sustainable mobility system.

1.2 Structure of the document

[Section 1](#) of this report presents the context and scope of Deliverable 5.2 together with a summary of its structure. [Section 2](#) introduces the concept of Influence Factor Analysis (IFA) and presents a literature review and empirical studies for the three areas of factors to be explored in terms of their potential influence on the perceived value of travel time, namely weather, ICT and transport infrastructure and services. The scope of IFA within MoTiV project is included in [Section 3](#) together with the presentation of all hypotheses and questions that will be examined as part of IFA. [Section 4](#) includes an overview of the data analysis methodology and tools used as well as some key

characteristics of the collected data which help to shape the profile of the different users engaged in the MoTiV data collection campaigns. The results of the data analysis are included in [Section 5](#) for the three areas under consideration (weather, ICT and transport infrastructure and services). Some explanatory data used for the analysis are presented in the beginning of Section 5 and the summary of the most valuable findings is presented in the end of the same section. Finally, a discussion on the approach, potential future work and next steps are presented in [Section 6](#).

2. Value of travel time and IFA in travel behaviour studies

This section introduces the concept of Influence Factor Analysis (IFA) and presents a literature review and empirical studies for the three areas of factors to be explored in terms of their potential influence on the perceived value of travel time, namely weather, ICT and transport infrastructure and services.

2.1 The purpose of Influence Factor Analysis

The influence factor analysis is a means to discover attributes and perceptions in travel behaviour that shape value of travel time. Conventional planning considers time and cost to be the primary contributors to value of travel time and consequently travel time savings. The MoTiV project questions this approach and aims to redefine VTT and shed light on other factors that play significant role on how travellers perceive travel time. For this purpose, influence factor analysis will be performed examining how different factors influence the worthwhileness ratings while travelling. Specifically, data collected from Woorti app will be used, mostly those focused in the following areas:

- Traveller (user) profile: socio-demographic details, transport preferences and attitudes towards travel time;
- Trip data: origin/destination, travel time, travel distance, modes of transport, travel purpose;
- Traveller's contextual assessment of worthwhile travel: traveller's trip rating in terms of worthwhileness, details on type of value (e.g. productivity, enjoyment, fitness) and activities carried out during the trip, and;
- Contextual experience factors: individual assessments on how features of the transport system (e.g. infrastructure, services, external conditions such as weather) influence mobility choices and perceived time value.

This dataset will be anonymised and accessible via the MoTiV project website and relevant Open Data repositories. This is a legacy of the project for future research on this topic. Further details on the data collection, data processing and different variables accounted for the analysis are presented in [Section 4](#) and [Section 5.1](#) of this report.

The influence factor analysis aims to continue the work done within *Deliverable 2.2 – Mobility and Travel Time* which is publicly available on MoTiV official website (<https://motivproject.eu/>). That deliverable developed the conceptual framework for redefining value of travel time and reviewed the relevant factors to be considered within this framework. It was concluded that the value of travel time depends on the three main components of Reasonable Travel Time which are door-to-door travel time, activities at the destination and the full experience while travelling. At the same time these elements

contribute in different ways according to age groups, gender, location, mode choices etc. Core to this approach and to the MoTiV project is to put the traveller and his/her perspective at the centre of the analysis. The analysis presented in this report therefore aims to reveal factors influencing the value of travel time as perceived by travellers in three thematic areas: ***weather, ICT and transport infrastructure and services.***

2.2 Empirical data on the areas of Influence Factor Analysis

This section analyses empirical studies aimed at identifying the effects of different factors on transport.

2.2.1 Weather

Weather is an important element affecting the transport of people and the associated urban planning. Weather affects travel behaviour, when it is possible to monitor the impact of weather on the choice of means of transport, and impacts the operation of the transport system as well. The focus of this analysis lies on understanding the direct impact of weather conditions on people's travel behaviour, in particular the impact on the perceived travel time worthwhileness while using different modes of transport. Understanding this would assist in designing appropriate transport policies for transport services and infrastructures, capable of mitigating or alleviating the negative effects of adverse weather on users' perception of travel time as well as providing more accurate travel demand forecast.

Based on the literature review, only few studies investigated the influence of the weather indicators and the corresponding variability on people's travel behaviour and mode choice. Whilst the previous studies are insightful, most of these studies were done only based on a relatively short period or based on a rather small geographical location. In this Deliverable, thanks to EU-wide dataset collected in MoTiV DCC countries, from May to December 2019, we will examine further the impacts of four weather indicators: temperature, clouds, precipitation and speed of the wind as experience factors on travel time worthwhileness across different modes of transport. Details on weather data collection can be found in [Section 4.2.2](#).

Findings from previous studies showed that the favourable weather (i.e. high temperatures without precipitation and wind) perceived by users will increase the interest in using active means of transport (walking, cycling). On the contrary, increased precipitation and wind speed increase usage of private motorised mode of transport or public transport (Bocker et al., 2016; Creemers et al., 2015; Sabir, 2011; Ahmed et al., 2010). However, it is necessary to focus on identifying the impact of weather on the choice of individual means of transport because the general assumption of the effect of weather may not apply for all. In the case of means of transport such as a cycling, it has been found that a temperature that is lower or higher than the optimum driving temperature has a negative impact on the choice of this transport mean (Bocker et al., 2016; Zhao et al., 2019). The choice of cycling is not only influenced by temperature but also by wind, rain conditions (in case of strong wind and heavy rain share of cycling significantly decreases), season and the impact rate of weather depends also on purpose of the trip, time and facilities (Liu et al., 2014; Gebhart & Noland, 2014; Zhao et al., 2019).

However, the effect of weather variability on modal choice is mostly contextual. But with modern forecast techniques and technology, people have learned to adjust their habits according to the surrounding weather to fit their utmost comfort. Yet, when they leave their comfort zone, weather influences their lifestyle in various ways. In most cases, bad weather increases the transit ridership. However, the adverse weather can also have a negative effect on the use of public transport e.g. on

weekends (Thao et al.,2020; Singhal et al., 2014). On weekdays the choice of modes of transport is influenced mainly by routine human behaviour, while over the weekend people are more willing to change choice of modes of transport based on the weather. The influence of weather on the choice of modes of transport can be also related to the destination. Some destinations that are easily reachable by public transport are less affected by weather conditions than those for which public transport needs to be combined with other modes of transport (Tao et al.,2018; Cools et al., 2010). When analysing the impact of weather on traffic, it is also important to keep in mind the difference among geographical locations. This factor has a significant impact on individual's reactions to different weather changes and their decisions in transport (Liu et al., 2014).

In this Deliverable, the weather impacts are analysed based on the predefined scenarios to assess people's perception of travel time worthwhileness. These results are reported in [Section 5.2.1](#).

2.2.2 ICT

The travel mode choice and the perception of the value of travel time are influenced by several factors such as accessibility, comfort, safety, environmental impact, and others. Nowadays, information and communication technologies are an integral part of daily lives, which massively impacts travel patterns, transport mode choice in particular.

The adoption and use of ICT offers new possibilities for combining travel, work, and leisure activities (Sheller and Urry 2006) and allows travellers to make a more worthwhile use of their travel time (Lyons and Urry 2005; Banerjee and Kanafani 2008).

Therefore, ICT can affect individuals' travel behaviour and transport demand, since it gives the possibilities to skip some trips and perform some activities remotely (teleworking, teleconference, e-commerce, e-learning, e-management) (Profillidis & Botzoris, 2019; Lyons, 2002). On the other hand, the use of ICT devices and availability of internet connectivity while travelling, will bring the possibility of performing more activities at the same time that is calling multi-tasking. For instance, Nathan (2019) in his research found that people who used electronic devices (smartphones, tablets or laptops) while travelling performed an average of 3 activities during their trip while people who did not use electronic devices performed only 1.

People use ICT during their trips mostly to communicate and listen to music, but they also work, study and have fun by watching videos or browsing the Internet (Gripsrud & Hjorthol, 2012; Nathan et al., 2019; Gamberini et al., 2013). These ICT-related activities can significantly affect the pleasantness and productivity of their travel time (Conolly et al, 2009).

Looking at ICT in terms of its application in transport services is currently mainly related to public transport. This has been argued in research focused on the use of ICT in public transport (Axtell et al., 2008; Nathan et al., 2019; Gripsrud & Hjorthol), 2012, Conolly et al., 2009; Freit et al., 2015). However, differences in use of ICT can also be identified within this category. In case of long-distance trip, using train provides better conditions for working and use of ICT use due to more stable rides and fewer stops than in other public transport modes (Ettema et al., 2012). Regarding walking or active modes of transport such as cycling, the use of ICT is mostly associated only with listening to music or using mobile applications e.g. for navigation. The use of ICT in cars depends on whether you are a driver or a passenger.

The basic factors influencing the use of ICT in transport relies on internet connectivity and the possibility of charging electronic devices. It should be noted that the availability of free Wi-Fi can trigger a wide range of use of ICT in public transport. However, some activities can be performed

without internet connectivity (e.g. listening to music) while on move, but most of the activities connected to use of ICT devices (e.g. instantaneous communication on social media or browsing the Internet) require internet connection (Nathan et al, 2019). The better internet connectivity associated with leisure activities can significantly influence the value of travel time (Nathan et al., 2019). Regarding the availability of charging opportunity, although long-distance modes of transport already have space for charging electronic devices, it cannot be provided for every passenger. These points for charging electronic devices may be occupied during the whole trip. This can limit the use of electronic devices by passengers and significantly affect the perception of travel time (Axtell et al., 2008).

The use of ICT can also be influenced by factors such as travelling alone or with someone, the length of the trip, the purpose of the trip, part of the day and others (Gamberini et al., 2013) and corresponds to a tremendous experience factor as shared and autonomous mobility proliferate.

In this deliverable, the effects of ICT-related activities (browsing, listening, watching and reading electronic devices) and ICT-related factors (i.e. internet connectivity and charging opportunities) on users' travel time worthwhileness will be analysed and reported in the [Section 5.2.2](#).

2.2.3 Transport infrastructure and services

The quality of transport infrastructure and provision of transport services impact the perceived experience and the way travellers value travel time. This section focuses on identifying factors resulting from transport infrastructure that affect people's satisfaction while travelling. Transport infrastructure can be defined as a network of the fixed installations of canals, waterways, airways, railways, roads, and terminals, as well as pipelines such as seaports, refuelling depots, trucking terminals, warehouses, bus stations, railway station, and airports (Hossain, 2019). Knowing the perception of the quality of transport infrastructure and the services provided can contribute to their improvement in the future.

One of the basic factors influencing people's travel time satisfaction is trip duration. Extending the trip duration can significantly affect the traveller's mood in a negative sense, because of rising stress, fatigue, painfulness (in some modes of transport) and sadness on long trips (Morris, Guerra, 2015; Zhu, Fan, 2018). However, the correlation between travel time and user satisfaction may also depend on travel mode (Kroesen, 2014) or the transport infrastructure itself.

Trip duration is also related to factors such as duration of transfers and reliability of travel time. Reliability of travel time has a significant impact on the perception of travel time especially over long distances. People who experience a delay on their trip are less satisfied than others. In the case of short distances, the decrease of satisfaction is not so significant, which may be due to several possibilities of replacing the means of transport with another. (Lunke, 2020). Considering public transport, the reliability of travel time is the most valued factor by users (Allen et al., 2018). Reliability can also affect the duration of transfers. Users negatively perceive transfers as they are associated with some uncertainty that causes discomfort to them (Chowdhury, 2015). Transfers should provide users with greater destination choices or to reduce travel time and costs which increases travel satisfaction (Bak et al., 2012). However, if the duration of transfer is very long, satisfaction is lower.

Other important factors are safety and security which are primary concerns when using any transport mode. In the literature, safety means being protected from danger, risk, or injury. The perception of safety is related to the protection against accidents and attacks while waiting or in the vehicle, disruption of the services or travelling too crowded during the trip (Allen, et al., 2019). On the other hand, security is the state of being free from danger or threat of harm or injury and perceived safety connected to negative experiences can significantly affect the choice of transport mode. Generally, the variables to predict and ensure safety are easier to examine, as they usually depend on a technical

solution. Security is more complex as this also depends on human interactions, which are less predictable, and depends on emotional rather than rational actions and reactions (Tsami et al. 2014).

There are many other factors related to transport infrastructure and the perceived experience of travel, such as simplicity of route, accessibility, vehicle ride smoothness, whose impact on the perception of travel time worthwhileness has been analysed and reported in [Section 5.2.3](#).

3. IFA scope and formulated hypotheses

This section outlines the scope of IFA within MoTiV project together with the presentation of all hypotheses and questions that will be examined as part of the data analysis.

3.1 Scope of Influence Factor Analysis within MoTiV

The MoTiV project framework is conceived around four pillars linked to the main areas of the Specific Objectives of the project. The four pillars are the conceptual, technological, organisational and analytical. The influence factor analysis presented in this report is the last step of the analytical pillar which deals with the analysis of the mobility and behavioural dataset, with the aim to demonstrate the suitability of the MoTiV conceptual framework to assess the Value of Travel Time. In order to fulfil this purpose, another three steps accompany IFA within the analytical pillar; multi-criteria clustering, which aims to identify similar behavioural travel patterns, matching behavioural patterns and value proposition of mobility, and cost benefit analysis from the perspective of Value of travel Time. The influence factor analysis will contribute together with these steps, to the evaluation of mobility behaviour data and validation of MoTiV framework in redefining VTT.

3.2 Hypotheses and questions for Influence Factor Analysis

This section presents those hypotheses and questions that were selected for implementing influence factor analysis on the available dataset. The research questions below aim to investigate how specific factors influence mobility choices and activities while on the move. When considered relevant, the research question is further examined across additional attributes such as age, gender, country, transport mode, trip purpose etc. The factors to be examined in terms of their influence on the perceived value of travel time are related to weather conditions, ICT and transport infrastructure and services.

The whole set of hypotheses is presented in detail in Deliverable 2.2 – Mobility and Travel Time which is publicly available on MoTiV official website. A total of 19 different hypotheses were formulated based on the conceptual framework developed for redefining travel time. As a follow-up activity, various research questions were formulated within each hypothesis to specify the type of analysis required. The coding of questions in the following tables follows this logic i.e. H15-Q2 refers to the second question within hypothesis 15. Among all the questions formulated within each hypothesis, only a sub-set of 18 was selected as appropriate for the influence factor analysis presented in this report. Questions were selected based on their relevance to the three focus areas of IFA. Moreover, some questions were excluded due to lack of data.

3.2.1 Weather conditions

Table 1 below shows the questions related to weather conditions as a factor influencing travel behaviour. “Today’s weather” was an available option among the different experience factors in Woorti app when the user was evaluating a trip leg, a common experience factor across all modes of transport. The analysis on weather as a factor influencing travel behaviour is further explored by assessing the impact of weather scenarios on mood and worthwhileness ratings. The weather scenarios have been created based on real time weather data collected while trips were taking place. Information on weather data collection can be found in [Section 4.2.2](#).

All questions selected for this analysis are part of Hypothesis 15 on Travel Comfort Factors which examines how the level of comfort and availability of services affect the value of travel time; weather is an external environmental factor that affects travel experience contributing to comfort levels while travelling. Such a factor can enhance or decrease the perceived value associated with journey time.

Hypothesis question	Research question	Details and Purpose
H15-Q2	What is the ranking of “Today’s weather” as an experience factor among all other factors?	Explore how important is “Today’s weather” as an experience factor across different modes of transport.
H15-Q8	What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and “Today’s weather” as an experience factor?	Is weather influencing the perceived value of travel time and worthwhileness ratings?
H15-Q13	What is the distribution of worthwhileness and mood ratings among different weather scenarios?	How are different weather scenarios associated with mood and worthwhileness ratings?
H15-Q14	What is the distribution of transport modes and worthwhileness ratings among different weather scenarios?	How are different weather scenarios associated with modal choice and worthwhileness ratings?

Table 1: Influence factor analysis research questions related to weather

3.2.2 Availability and use of ICT

The growing availability of ICT plays a significant role and can have both positive and negative impacts on the value of travel time as experienced by travellers. The ICT related research questions at Table 2 below form Hypothesis 13 on Smartphone-based Activities. There were several ICT related activities users of Woorti app could select from; “Browsing or social media”, “Reading / writing (device)”, “Listening to audio” and “Watching video or gaming”. It will be sought if these activities contribute to low or high ratings of worthwhileness. Furthermore, two experience factors related to ICT availability, “Internet connectivity” and “Charging opportunity”, will be examined across different modes of transport, to find out if they influence worthwhileness ratings.

Hypothesis question	Research question	Details and Purpose
H13-Q1	What are the ICT activities that are more frequently associated with worthwhileness ratings?	The ICT related activities are “Browsing or social media”, “Reading / writing (device)”, “Listening to audio”, “Watching video or gaming”.
H13-Q2	What is the correlation between worthwhileness and ICT activities?	The goal is to understand to what extent low or high values of worthwhileness ratings are associated with any ICT activities.
H13-Q3	What is the role of ICT in shaping VTT: how are the two factors “Internet connectivity” and “Charging opportunity” correlated to travel worthwhileness?	It will be explored the influence of experience factors related to ICT availability on worthwhileness ratings.

Table 2: Influence factor analysis research questions related to ICT

3.2.3 Transport infrastructure and services

The quality of transport infrastructure and provision of transport services impact the perceived experience and the way travellers value travel time. This domain will be explored through several research questions across five different hypotheses since transport infrastructure and services relate to multiple sectors and stages of a journey. In particular, it will be explored how smoothness of travel in terms of number of trip legs, total waiting time in a trip and types of transfers between modes affect

the overall mood following a trip. It is noted that mood here is a proxy of the responses to the Woorti question "Overall, how did you feel about this trip?". Further clarification on mood vs worthwhileness assessments can be found in [Section 4](#). These research questions are all part of Hypothesis 1 on Door-to-door time which aims to assess the efficiency of connectivity of trips.

Another dimension to be explored is reliability and how this affects worthwhileness ratings or how often it is reported as a negative or positive experience factor. "Reliability" was one of the experience factors available for users to select when evaluating a trip leg using public transport and "Predictability" was the respective term for active modes and private motorised transport. These research questions form Hypothesis 2 on Reliable door-to-door time which explores the importance of reliability on mode choice.

One research question is selected from Hypothesis 9 which aims to identify the top negative experience factors for trip legs performed by alternative modes to motorised transport among car users. The intention of this research question is to identify the potential for shifting to alternative modes of transport compared to motorised travel. Furthermore, a total of four research questions are selected from Hypothesis 15 on Travel Comfort Factors, which will explore the top positive and negative experience factors, comfort travel factors across different transport modes and if there is any correlation of comfort factors to worthwhileness ratings or the activities performed while travelling.

Finally, another two research questions relate to Hypothesis 16 on Jerkiness as a Proxy for Comfort which examines travel comfort and the level of engagement in worthwhile tasks when vibration, jerkiness and shock levels are involved. The experience factors reflecting the essence of this hypothesis are "Road path quality" and "Road path directness" in active transport and "Vehicle ride smoothness" in both public and private transport. The importance of these experience factors on worthwhileness ratings will be explored and when negative experience was reported by users, the associated activities selected from the user will be identified.

Hypothesis question	Research question	Details and Purpose
H1-Q1	Is there a correlation between number of legs and the mood within a trip?	The results of the research question will indicate the efficiency of connectivity and if trips legs are well integrated. Multiple connections increase unwanted travel efforts which affect the mood.
H1-Q2	Is there a correlation between trip duration, duration of transfers (i.e. waiting time) and the mood?	Duration of transfers is the total waiting time for the whole trip. Indicates if smoothness of travel, which relates to less unwanted travel efforts, affects the mood.
H1-Q5	Which types of transfer are more significant in terms of high or low levels of mood?	To explore which types of transfers affect the mood most. The type of transfer is defined by the different combinations of transfers between transport modes.
H2-Q1	How is the reliability of travel time related to worthwhile assessments?	Examine if and how reliability as an experience factor affects worthwhileness levels by gender, transport mode category, trip purpose, country, weekday/weekend.
H9-Q3	What are the negative experience factors for trip legs performed by alternative modes for users of motorised transport?	To understand what is the potential for shifting to other modes.
H15-Q1	What are the top positive and negative experience factors?	To explore the most frequent satisfactory and unsatisfactory experience factors.

H15-Q3	What is the distribution of top satisfaction/dissatisfaction factors related to “Crowdedness and Seating availability” in public transport modes?	To explore comfort travel factors in public transport.
H15-Q7	What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and satisfaction factors?	Examine if the impact of experience factors on worthwhileness values changes according to transport mode, gender and country.
H15-Q9	What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and satisfaction factors and activities?	Study further any correlation of activities with satisfaction levels and worthwhileness values.
H16-Q1	How are experience factors related to “Smoothness” correlated to worthwhileness?	Smoothness as an experience factor is represented by “Road path quality” and “Road path directness” in active transport and “Vehicle ride smoothness” in both public and private transport.
H16-Q2	When factors on smoothness are negatively rated, what are the activities that are carried out while on the move (and how does that compare to “normal” list of activities when this factor is not mentioned)?	To explore which activities are present when experience factors related to “Smoothness” are rated negatively and further explore if these activities are among the most frequent ones when “Smoothness” related experience factors are not selected.

Table 3: Influence factor analysis research questions related to transport infrastructure and services

4. Data

This section presents an overview of the data used for the analysis described in the rest of the document. This section is structured as follows: in Section 4.1, the data analysis tools and methodologies are introduced, focusing on how appropriate tools were chosen for the IFA. Section 4.2 presents a description of the most relevant data collected for this deliverable together with the data pre-processing steps. Finally, some key statistics are presented from the collected dataset in Section 4.3.

4.1 Data analysis tools and methodology

In this section, the tools and methodologies used for the influence factor analysis are presented together with the rationale behind the choices that led to this setup.

Python³ was used for interpreting data and analysing the results of MoTiV EU-wide dataset. Python is an interpreted, high-level, general-purpose programming language with a variety of powerful features, widely used in the context of data science.

Python has become a de facto standard in data science: many classical algorithms used in data science, such as clustering or conditionality reduction, are already available in well-known, well-tested libraries. For this reason, Python has become the language of choice for many data scientists.

Python libraries are well-known for the variety of the algorithms implemented and for their efficiency. They are the industry reference standard for data analysis. Reusing these libraries has allowed a focus on fine-tuning the data analysis instead of having to reimplement the algorithms themselves. The most relevant libraries that were used are:

- Pandas⁴ and NumPy⁵ for querying data and numerical analysis;
- SciPy⁶ for advanced algorithms;
- Matplotlib⁷, seaborn⁸, and Plotly⁹ for visualizations and plots.

For analysing the MoTiV Dataset, Jupyter notebooks have been used. Jupyter notebooks are a web-based, interactive computational environment. A Jupyter notebook document contains input and output cells that can contain code, text (using a simplified formatting language called Markdown), mathematical expressions, plots, images, and other hypertextual media. With notebooks, it is possible to write data analysis pipelines interposed with rich explanations, containing text, equations, and pictures. Jupyter notebooks are a useful tool for an open and reproducible science (Randles, 2017) way to share data analyses and a new tool for scientific communications that will make the traditional scientific paper obsolete¹⁰.

³ <https://www.python.org>, visited on 2020-05-05

⁴ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>, accessed on 2020-05-05

⁵ <https://numpy.org/>, accessed on 2020-05-05

⁶ <https://www.scipy.org/>, accessed on 2020-05-05

⁷ <https://matplotlib.org/>, accessed on 2020-05-05

⁸ <https://seaborn.pydata.org/>, accessed on 2020-05-05

⁹ <https://plotly.com/python/> accessed on 2020-05-05

¹⁰ «[The Scientific Paper Is Obsolete](#)», The Atlantic, April 5, 2018, accessed 2020-05-05

The choice of Python was deemed necessary in order to process the data gathered through the Woorti app. The data, as described in *Deliverable D3.4 – MoTiV App* (www.motivproject.eu), was encoded in the JSON format: JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is an open standard file format, and data interchange format, that uses human-readable text to store and transmit data objects consisting of attribute-value pairs and array data types.

While very flexible, the JSON format needs to be processed to be converted in other formats, such as tabular data. For this task, the flexibility of a programming language is needed. While the most common data analyses software, like Excel, can work with tabular data or other compatible formats such as CSV files, they are not able to handle many other formats.

In addition, Python was chosen because of its ability to handle the scale of data in MoTiV. While the data analysed cannot be described as "Big Data", pre-packaged analysis tools may not be able to handle the hundreds of thousands of records that we gathered in the project. Python has proven to be scalable, and it is commonly used in Big Data projects.

Finally, we should mention the fact that other data-science oriented languages could be utilized to perform the data analysis, such as R or Julia. Python was chosen instead because it is the language where the data analysis team had the most experience and for the variety of established libraries available for data science.

4.2 Data collection and pre-processing

The data was collected between from May 1st to December 16th, 2019 using the Woorti mobile app, designed and developed within the scope of the project. The app automatically detected trips and modes as well as changes between modes, which appeared in a travel log. Users were then prompted to select detected trips for validation and for entering further details regarding their travel experience. Data collection was facilitated by dedicated national data collection campaigns, coordinated by project campaign managers; these campaigns took place in 8 European countries: Belgium, Finland, France, Italy, Norway, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain. In addition, data was also collected in Croatia and Other countries.

The use of the app consists of three main phases:

1. *Onboarding*: upon installing the application and registering a new account, the user is introduced to the functionalities of the app. During this process, the user enters her travel preferences in terms of typical modes and travel time use, as well as, optionally, basic demographic information.
2. *Trip recording*: the app automatically detects the start of a trip by monitoring the phone sensors, and attempts to distinguish trip legs and transport modes (for example walking, cycling, car, bus, tram or train).
3. *Trip validation*: when a trip finishes, the user can validate it, provide more precision on the transport mode (e.g. car passenger or car driver), and answer a number of trip-level questions (trip purpose, mood, etc). The user is then prompted to elect a specific leg (and therefore a specific mode) to answer further questions about the key worthwhileness variables (worthwhileness assessment, value, travel activities, and assessment of positive and negative experience factors).

Tables 4 and 5 below describe the data collected from the application during the onboarding step and trip recording and validation steps respectively.

	Name	Description and Admissible values
Worthwhileness values	Generic worthwhileness (F, E, P)	Overall evaluation of how much fitness, enjoyment, and productivity matter for a user's travel experiences ([0-100])
	Specific worthwhileness (F, E, P)	Evaluation for each preferred mode of transport of how much fitness, enjoyment, and productivity matter for a user's travel experiences using that mode of transport ([0-100])
Demographics	Gender	Male, Female, Other
	Education level	Basic, High school, or University
	Language	Catalan, Dutch, English, Finnish, French, Italian, Norwegian, Portuguese, Slovak, Spanish and Croatian
	Age range	16-19, 20-24, 25-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-64, 65-74, 75+
	Marital Status	Divorced, Married, Registered partnership, Single, Widowed
	Labour Status	Employed full-time, Employed part-time, Pensioner, Student, Unemployed

Table 4: User data collected during the onboarding phase – Demographic information was optional

	Name	Description and Admissible values
Recording	Trip id	Identifier of the trip the leg refers to
	User id	Identifier of the who performed the travel leg
	Leg duration	Leg travel time expressed in minutes
	Leg distance	Leg travel distance expressed in meters
	Mode of transport	Mode of transport used; there are 37 different modes of transport
	Transport category	Transport category associated to the transport mode; there are 5 different categories (Cycling and emerging micromobility ¹¹ , Private motorized, Public transport short distance, Public transport long distance, Walking and running)
	Evaluation	Worthwhileness evaluation
Mood evaluation		Mood evaluation for a trip. Mood relates to the overall question "How did you feel about this trip?". The mood rating for a trip is given on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high).

Table 5: Trip recording and evaluation data

Within the application, a user can access her data through several screens and visualise and edit her profile information and trips. Furthermore, the application features a dashboard that presents to the

¹¹ Micromobility is defined, by the International Transport Forum, as the use of micro-vehicles with a speed of up to 45km/h and a mass of up to 350kg (https://www.itf-oecd.org/sites/default/files/docs/safe-micromobility_1.pdf)

user multiple statistics related to her validated trips, both at an individual level and by comparison with the app community.

User preferences and experiences are encoded in two main sets of values, called *worthwhileness values*:

- *generic worthwhileness values*: they are a triplet of values *F*, *E*, and *P* for *fitness*, *enjoyment*, and *productivity*, respectively. They measure how much the user values these dimensions in general when travelling;
- *specific worthwhileness values*: they are triplets of values *F*, *E*, and *P* that the user is asked to assign for each specific mode of transport that she chooses in the onboarding phase. The transport modes that the user selects during the onboarding phase are called *preferred transport modes*. Specific worthwhileness values are the measure of how much the user values *fitness*, *enjoyment*, and *productivity* when using that particular transport mode.

In addition, user trip evaluation is comprised of two overall dimensions:

- *Worthwhileness score*: a general evaluation of how much the time spent during the trip was considered worthwhile. The general worthwhileness score of a trip is encoded in a scale from 1 (time was wasted) to 5 (time was worthwhile);
- *Mood rating*: a rating of the mood of the user. Mood relates to the overall question “How did you feel about this trip?”. The mood rating for a trip is given on a scale from 1 (low) to 5 (high).

During the onboarding phase, the user is asked to provide both the generic and specific worthwhileness values on a scale from 1 to 100. When evaluating trips, the user is asked to provide an evaluation for each dimension of *fitness*, *enjoyment*, and *productivity* using a scale from low to high (low, medium, high).

Each trip is composed of trip parts, that can be either a *leg* - i.e., a part of a journey when the app has detected some movement - or a *waiting event* - that corresponds to the user not moving. When the app detects that a new trip part has started, it records the initial and final locations and timestamps. Furthermore, when creating a leg, the app infers a predicted mode of transport; within a leg, other statistics regarding trip time duration, speed and acceleration are collected. In the case of a waiting event, the app registers the average location. At the end of a trip users can review and validate the data collected. Since this requires an extra effort to the user, the app offers a set of incentives for users (e.g., personalized statistics in the app dashboard, point system, possibility of connecting points to campaign rewards) to validate as many trips as possible. This approach preserves the privacy of the user, since she can choose which trips to validate and submit to the server.

Each trip is assigned to a transport category based on the mode of transport of the reviewed leg; this leg – selected by the user during trip validation – is considered to be the main leg of the trip. The different transport mode categories are presented in [Section 5.1](#).

The limitation of the possibility of evaluating one leg per-trip was designed to shorten the number of questions and effort required by the user in reporting trips. While a trip can contain several legs, the user is informed that she can report information just for one leg and that the evaluation refers to the whole trip.

4.2.1 Data pre-processing

To obtain the data used for the analysis, it was first pre-processed performing four main tasks:

1. data cleaning: duplicate or incomplete data was removed;
2. automatic merging of similar legs: trip legs were automatically merged when all of the following conditions were met: a) they belonged to the same user; b) they had the same mode of transport; and c) the time difference between the ending time of the first leg and the starting time of the second was less than 5 minutes;
3. outlier removal: to reduce noise in the data, extremely long and short legs were eliminated by removing legs belonging to the first and last percentile of the distribution of legs – for each different transport mode – in terms of distance (leg distance) and time (leg duration). Trips containing one or more outlier legs were eliminated altogether;
4. user removal: users that did not have any trip left at the end of the previous steps were eliminated.

It is pointed out that since the analysis presented in this report encompass several aspects of each trip that was recorded through the MoTiV application, each question analysed required a different selection and filtering from this initial set of users and trips. In many cases, questions were optional, or users could provide a variety of different answers. In some cases, during the analysis, it was found that some user choices were unexpected or did not conform to the app specifications. Hence, on a case by case basis, it was examined if these spurious values could be reconducted to some valid answers or if they needed to be discarded completely. For these reasons, the totals appearing in different analysis may differ from one another.

4.2.2 Weather Data

Weather data was collected by INESC-ID through the API provided by the OpenWeatherMap online service¹². OpenWeatherMap is an online service owned by OpenWeather Ltd, a company based in London, United Kingdom. The API was queried regularly to obtain weather data for a set of cities of interest in the scope of the project as shown at Table 6 below. Weather info was collected for the times of 09:00, 12:00 and 18:00 for each day from 08/07/2019 to 18/12/2019.

For the computation of weather scenarios, information was combined about cloud coverage, precipitation, wind speed and apparent temperature. In particular, the apparent temperature was computed, which is equivalent of the temperature perceived by humans, based on effects of air temperature, relative humidity and wind speed. The formula for apparent temperature introduced by Robert Steadman in 1984 (Steadman, 1984) was used, which takes into consideration four environmental factors: wind, temperature, humidity and radiation from the sun. The formula for the apparent temperature (AT) is:

$$AT = T_a + 0.348 \cdot e - 0.70 \cdot ws + 0.70 \frac{Q}{ws + 10} - 4.25$$

where:

- T_a is the dry bulb temperature (in °C);
- e is the water vapor pressure (in hPa);

¹² OpenWeatherMap: <https://openweathermap.org/>

- ws is the wind speed at an elevation of 10 meters (in m/s);
- Q is the net radiation absorbed per unit area of body surface (in W/m²).

The water vapor pressure (e) is computed as:

$$e = \frac{rh}{100} \cdot 6.105 \cdot e^{\frac{17.27 - a}{237.7 + T_a}}$$

and rh is the relative humidity (%).

While temperature (T_a), relative humidity (rh), and windspeed data (ws) were available from the OpenWeatherMap API, to obtain net radiation data (Q) <https://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/> another data source was used.

Net radiation data were downloaded from the NASA Earth Observatory (NASA-NEO) website¹³, which publishes daily maps of the net radiation absorbed by Earth. These data are available in several machine-readable formats, such as GeoTIFF or CSV, and can be downloaded <https://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/> in bulk via FTP¹⁴.

Portugal	Slovakia	Finland	Spain	Belgium
Lisbon	Žilina	Helsinki	Barcelona	Antwerp
Porto	Bratislava	Tampere	Girona	Brugge
	Trnava	Turku	Tarragona	Brussels
	Nitra	Oulu	Lleida	Gent
	Trenčín	Etelä-Suomi		Leuven
	Banská Bystrica	Itä-Suomi		
	Košice	Pohjois-Suomi		
	Prešov	Keski-Suomi		
		Länsi-Suomi		
Italy	France	Norway	Croatia	
Milan	Paris	Oslo	Zagreb	
	Lyon	Bergen	Velika Gorica	
	Grenoble	Trondheim	Samobor	
	Nevers	Stavager	Zaprešić	
	Nantes	Drammen	Dugo selo	
	Bordeaux	Fredrikstad	Zagrebačka županija	
	Toulouse	Porsgrunn	Split	
	Strasbourg	Skien	Rijeka	
	Amiens	Kristiansand	Osijek	
	Angers	Ålesund	Varaždin	
	Lille	Tønsberg	Zadar	
	Brest			
	Marseille			
	Saint Brieuc			
	Montpellier			

Table 6: Cities for which weather info was obtained from OpenWeatherMap

¹³ NASA Earth Observatory (NASA-NEO), <https://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

¹⁴ Daily net radiation data GeoTIFF are available for bulk download at: https://neo.sci.gsfc.nasa.gov/archive/geotiff.float/CERES_NETFLUX_D/

4.3 Sample of users and characteristics, key statistics from the dataset

With the app, data was collected from 3,384 users, consisting of 71,509 validated trips and 179,679 legs. After pre-processing, described in [Section 4.2.1](#) above, the final dataset was comprised of 3,269 unique users, with a total of 64,098 validated trips and 158,897 trip legs.

Table 7 presents the number of trips and users for each transport mode category. Since a user could choose multiple preferred modes of transport and perform multiple trips, the sum of users is greater than the number of unique users. Trips shown at the table below refer only to trips with a valid transport mode and for those users that have validated at least one trip.

Category	Trips		Users	
	#	f(%)	#	f(%)
Cycling and Micromobility	11023	21.99	1317	43.74
Private Motorised	15003	29.93	1741	57.82
PT long-distance	481	0.96	189	5.28
PT short-distance	6097	12.16	1211	40.22
Walking	17529	34.96	2124	70.54
TOTAL	50133	100	6582	-

Table 7: Number (#) and fraction expressed as a percentage (f) of trips by transport category (trips) and users with at least one trip in that category (Users)

Figure 1 shows some insights into the demographics of users. More than half of the users are male, and half of the users are between 30 and 49 years old. Furthermore, taking into account that less than 30% of users declared their education level, marital or labour status, 80% of those users that reported this information have a university degree, 42% are married while 39% are single; 69% have a full-time job while 16% are students.

Figure 1: Demographic characteristics of users. Left to right: distribution of gender, age ranges, education level, marital and labour status

Table 8 shows the number of users by gender, together with how many trips and legs were performed and validated. In the following we will present a segmentation by gender for several analysis, however, we do not show the results for users who choose Other as gender because of the limited number of trips and legs performed.

	Users	Trips	Legs
Male	1844	38981	98321
Female	1410	24986	60173
Other	15	131	403
Total	3269	64098	158897

Table 8: Number of users, number of trips and legs validated by gender

Figures 2 and 3 show the distribution of number of users and trip legs by gender for each of the countries where data collection campaigns have been performed.

Figure 2: Number of users by gender and country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

Figure 3: Number of trip legs by gender and country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the distribution of trip legs across different worthwhileness values and the distribution of trips across different mood values respectively by gender.

Figure 4: Distribution of trip legs across worthwhileness ratings by gender

Figure 5: Distribution of trips across mood ratings by gender

Figure 6 shows the number of trip legs (y axis) for every worthwhileness category (E - enjoyment, F - fitness, Pw - Paid work, and Pt - Personal tasks) and their evaluation (0 - none, 1 - some, 2 - high) across age groups. Figure 7 shows average values (y axis) for all worthwhileness ratings from 1 to 5 in different categories (x axis) across age groups.

Figure 6: Distribution of worthwhileness categories by age

Figure 7: Distribution of worthwhileness elements by age

Figure 8 shows the distribution of the number of trip legs across different modes of transport and Figure 9 shows the number of trip legs performed by different mode categories in different countries. It is noted that modal share shown in Figure 6 is calculated based on the number of trip legs validated by all users of the app and “walking” is often part of transfers to other modes of transport.

Figure 8: Modal split based on the number of validated trip legs for all transport modes

Figure 9: Modal split based on transport mode categories (C – Cycling & Emerging Micromobility, Pm – Private Motorised, PTI – Public Transport Long Distance, PTs – Public Transport Short Distance, W - Walking) of all trip legs by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

Figures 10 and 11 show the distributions of travel time in minutes and distance travelled in meters respectively for all trips.

Figure 10: Distribution of duration of travel time (in minutes) for all trip legs

Figure 11: Distribution of distance travelled (in meters) for all trip legs

5. Results

This section presents some explanatory data used for the analysis which will be useful for the interpretation of the results. The results of the data analysis for the three areas under consideration (weather, ICT and transport infrastructure and services) comprise the main part of this section together with a summary of the most valuable findings.

5.1 Explanatory data used for the analysis

This section presents a few sets of data which were formulated in order to fit the scope of the influence factor analysis. All design decisions related to the collection of suitable data, as presented in this section, for assessing travel time experience are described in Deliverable 2.3, Deliverable 3.2 and the paper prepared by Cornet et al. (2019).

All transport modes for which trip legs were recorded and validated are presented at Table 9 below categorised in the 5 transport mode categories used for the data analysis. Transport modes are presented only when more than 1 trip leg was assigned to it. A few more options were available to users which were not selected. The order of modes within each category is descending in relation to their frequency. In addition, highlighted are those transport modes where the user is potentially involved in driving activities (driving modes) with the rest of the modes classified as non-driving. This classification was used for the allocation of different activities to the available modes of transport as shown at the following Table 10.

Private motorised	Public Transport Long Distance	Public Transport Short Distance	Walking	Cycling & Emerging Micromobility
Private Car (Driver)	Regional/Intercity Train	Bus/Trolley Bus	Walking	Bicycle
Private Car (Passenger)	High-speed Train	Metro	Jogging/Running	Electric Bicycle
Taxi/Ride Hailing	Coach/Long-distance Bus	Urban Train		Bike Sharing
Motorcycle	Airplane	Tram		Micro Scooter
Car Sharing/Rental (Driver)	Ferry/Boat			Cargo Bike
Car Sharing/Rental (Passenger)				
Moped				
Other Private Motorised				

Table 9: Transport mode categories together with a classification of driving (highlighted) and non-driving modes

The available activities when users were validating a trip leg are shown in Table 10 below. Their application to driving or non-driving modes of transport as defined in Table 9 above is also presented at the second column.

Activities	Applied to
Driving / Cycling / Walking	Driving
Relaxing or sleeping	Non-driving
Browsing or social media	All
Reading / writing (paper)	Non-driving
Reading / writing (device)	Non-driving

Listening to audio	All
Watching video or gaming	Non-driving
Talking (including phone)	All
Accompanying someone	All
Eating / drinking	All
Personal caring	All
Thinking	All
Other	All

Table 10: Available activities and application to driving/non driving modes of transport

Table 11 below presents all experience factors which were available to users of Woorti app for different modes of transport. Experience factors are grouped within Activities, Getting there, Comfort and Pleasantness and While you ride which is only applicable to Public Transport. Some of the experience factors were the same or similar across all modes while others were only available in some of them.

Public Transport (Short and Long Distance)	Active Transport (Walking & Emerging Micromobility)	Private Motorised
Activities	Activities	Activities
Ability to do what I want while I travel	Ability to do what I want while I travel	Ability to do what I wanted
Getting there	Getting there	Getting there
Simplicity/difficulty of the route	Simplicity/difficulty of the route	Simplicity/difficulty of the route
Reliability of travel time	Road/path availability and safety	Traffic congestion/delays
Security and safety	Good accessibility (escalators, lifts, ramps, etc.)	Predictability of travel time
Space for luggage/pram/bicycle etc.	Traffic signals/crossings	Security and safety
Ability to take kids or pets along	Route planning/navigation tools	Space for luggage/pram/bicycle etc.
Payment and tickets	Information and signs	Ability to take kids or pets along
Good accessibility (lifts, boarding, etc.)	Ability to carry bags, luggage etc.	Route planning/navigation tools
Route planning/navigation tools	Ability to take kids or pets along	Information and signs
Information and signs	Crowding/congestion	Parking at end points
Check-in, security and boarding	Predictability of travel time	Comfort and pleasantness
While you ride	Benches/toilets etc.	Today's weather
Crowdedness/seat availability	Facilities (shower, lockers)	Road quality/vehicle ride smoothness
Internet connectivity	Parking at end points	Vehicle quality
Charging opportunity	Comfort and pleasantness	Charging opportunity
Tables	Today's weather	Privacy
Toilets	Road/path quality	Seat comfort
Food/drink allowed	Road/path directness	Noise level
Food/drink available	Noise level	Air quality/temperature
Shopping/retail	Air quality	Urban scenery and atmosphere
Entertainment	Lighting/visibility	Nature and scenery

Car/bike parking at transfer point	Urban scenery and atmosphere	Other passengers
Comfort and pleasantness	Nature and scenery	Other cars/vehicles
Today's weather	Other people	
Vehicle ride smoothness	Cars/other vehicles	
Seating quality/personal space		
Other people		
Privacy		
Noise level		
Air quality/temperature		
Cleanliness		
General atmosphere/design		
Scenery		

Table 11: Experience factors available for different transport modes

Table 12 below shows the trip purposes users of the app could choose from as well as the categorisation used for the influence factor analysis in the second column.

Trip Purposes available in Woorti app	Trip Purpose Categories
Home	Home
Work	Work
Business trip	
Leisure/Hobby	Leisure
Everyday shopping	Shopping
School/Education	Education
Pick-up/Drop-off someone	Other
Personal tasks/Errand	
Trip itself	
Other	

Table 12: Trip purpose categories and correspondence with available options in Woorti app

5.2 Data analysis results

This section presents the results derived from the statistical analysis of the data presented above. The results are presented for each one of the three different focus groups of the influence factor analysis together with their respective research questions within each hypothesis as those presented at [Section 3.3](#).

5.2.1 Weather conditions

As shown at Table 1 in [Section 3.2.1](#) above, a few research questions are targeted to factor analysis of weather conditions which are presented below together with the main findings and interpretation. To perform this influence factor analysis, weather scenarios were created based on four different variables in collected weather data: intensity of clouds, precipitation levels, wind and temperature. For each one of these variables, a few categories were created based on the intensity levels or the comfort human factor. Furthermore, before performing travel behaviour analysis on weather data, the reported air temperature was converted into apparent temperature to represent more accurately what people feel.

The final seven weather scenarios formulated for this analysis are presented in Table 13 below together with the categories applicable for each scenario. The first scenario represents good or neutral weather conditions with no clouds or clear sky category (which includes few clouds), no or light precipitation category, light breeze wind category and comfortable temperature category defined according to humans which is between 15°C and 25°C (Böcker, 2016). The remaining six scenarios were shaped by keeping one main variable constant and all the rest without any restrictions. For example, the cold scenario includes those trip legs that were performed while temperature was cold (<15°C) without applying any filter for the remaining variables. Further details on the variables and definition of categories are presented in [Appendix 1](#) of this report.

#	Weather scenarios	Clouds	Precipitation	Wind	Temperature
1	Neutral/Good	No clouds or Clear sky	No or Light precipitation	Light breeze	Comfortable
2	Cold	Any	Any	Any	Cool
3	Warm	Any	Any	Any	Warm
4	Uncomfortable temperature	Any	Any	Any	Uncomfortably Cold or Uncomfortably Hot
5	Rainy/Snowy	Any	Moderate or Heavy precipitation	Any	Any
6	Cloudy	Partially Cloudy or Completely Cloudy	Any	Any	Any
7	Windy	Any	Any	Strong breeze or Gale	Any

Table 13: Weather scenarios and categories for each variable

H15-Q2 What is the ranking of “Today’s weather” as an experience factor among all other factors?

The purpose of this question is to explore the importance of “Today’s weather” as an experience factor among all experience factors reported by users across different modes of transport. Table 14 below shows the top 10 most frequent experience factors reported by the users of Woorti app in five transport mode categories. It should be noted that some experience factors were common in all transport modes while some factors were only applicable to specific transport modes. The full list of available experience factors for all transport mode categories is presented in [Section 5.1](#) above.

The data presented at the following table reveals that Today’s Weather was reported among the top 10 most frequent experience factors in all transport mode categories apart from Public Transport (PT) used for Short Distance trips. This finding is in alignment with empirical evidence as those presented in [Section 2.2.1](#) of this report. In particular, Today’s Weather is the most frequent experience factor selected by cyclists and the second one for those walking and those travelling with private motorised modes. For public transport modes, Today’s Weather is among the top 10 experience factors for long distance journeys but this factor was not among the most frequently selected for trip legs performed by short distance PT modes which are metro, tram, bus, trolley bus and urban train in which case other factors were considered more important. It is noted that users could report either a negative or positive contribution of experience factors to the perceived quality of travel time.

	Cycling & Emerging Micromobility	Walking
1	Todays_Weather	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route
2	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	Todays_Weather
3	Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted
4	Road_Path_Quality	Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety
5	Road_Path_Directness	Road_Path_Quality

6	Air_Quality	Scenery
7	Scenery	Road_Path_Directness
8	Cars_Other_Vehicles	Air_Quality
9	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	Other_People
10	Noise_Level	Noise_Level
	PT long distance	PT short distance
1	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route
2	Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time
3	Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted
4	Crowdedness_Seating	Crowdedness_Seating
5	Scenery	Seating_Quality_Personal_Space
6	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness
7	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	Scenery
8	Today's_Weather	Security_And_Safety
9	Security_And_Safety	Payment_And_Tickets
10	Internet_Connectivity	Other_People
	Private Motorised	
1	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	
2	Today's_Weather	
3	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	
4	Traffic_Congestion_Delays	
5	Vehicle_Quality	
6	Parking_At_End_Points	
7	Scenery	
8	Road_Quality_Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	
9	Other_Passengers	
10	Seat_Comfort	

Table 14: Top 10 experience factors reported as positive or negative in different transport mode categories

Further analysis on top positive and negative experience factors is presented within H15-Q1 in [Section 5.2.3](#).

H15-Q8 What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and “Today’s weather” as an experience factor?

This question is analysed by distributing all 5 values of worthwhileness for those trip legs that “Today’s weather” was rated positively or negatively by users when assessing the quality of travel time. Worthwhileness ratings range from 1 to 5 representing a scale from wasted to worthwhile time and they were values assigned to trip legs by users as part of a full door-to-door trip validation. It is noted that all figures below present worthwhileness ratings from 1 to 5 at the x axis and the frequency of “Today’s weather” reported as a negative or positive factor of a trip leg on the y axis.

The purpose of this question is to explore if weather influences the perceived value of travel time and worthwhileness ratings. The analysis is performed by gender, transport mode category and country with both positive and negative contribution of weather to the perceived value of travel time. Figure 12 below shows that positive contribution of “Today’s weather” to the value of travel time is reported more frequently for trip legs with higher worthwhileness ratings. The negative contribution of “Today’s weather” was more evenly reported across the different values of worthwhileness. It should be also noted that this pattern is followed more by male users compared to female users of the app which is expected since 62% of trip legs were validated by male users.

Figure 12: Frequency of “Today’s weather” as a positive or negative experience factor across worthwhileness values, by gender

Interestingly, as shown in Figure 13 below, trip legs in Walking category present similar negative and positive contribution of weather as an experience factor in different worthwhileness ratings which is also increasing for higher values. This result indicates that for those walking, jogging or running, a negative experience with weather, such as adverse conditions, does not affect an overall worthwhile trip. A similar trend is also observed in Cycling & Emerging Micromobility category but with more frequent positive experience reported compared to negative in terms of weather when values of worthwhileness are high. This result indicates that weather affects the perceived value of travel time for those using Cycling & Emerging Micromobility modes compared to those Walking, where negative and positive evaluations were similar. In private motorised modes, “Today’s weather” was reported as a negative factor more evenly across all values of worthwhileness, while more trip legs had a positive experience on “Today’s weather” when the trip was valued higher for its worthwhileness. In public transport modes, for trips with a worthwhileness value between 3 and 5 (where the majority of values stand), positive and negative evaluations of weather seem to have a proportional relation with worthwhileness ratings; when values of worthwhileness increase, positive evaluations of weather as an experience factor increase as well while the negative ones decrease.

Figure 13: Frequency of “Today’s weather” as a positive or negative experience factor across worthwhileness values, by transport mode category

Figure 14 below shows the distribution of positive and negative perceived contribution of weather in different values of worthwhileness across different countries. Each country presents different distributions and it is hard to identify a common pattern or behaviour.

Figure 14: Frequency of “Today’s weather” as a positive or negative experience factor across worthwhileness values, by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

H15-Q13 What is the distribution of worthwhileness and mood ratings among different weather scenarios?

This question explores how different weather scenarios associate with mood and worthwhileness ratings. Mood ratings are represented by the results of the Woorti question "Overall, how did you feel about this trip?" which had a 5-star scale ranging from "Lousy" to "Great". This was the first question users had to answer in the validation process, evaluating the whole trip. Worthwhileness ratings refer to trip legs performed by specific transport modes and the 5-star scale ranged from “All time was wasted” to “All time was worthwhile”. Weather scenarios and definition of variables are presented in detail in the beginning of this [Section 5.2.1](#). It is noted that one trip or trip leg can be part of more than one weather scenario.

Figure 15: Distribution of mood ratings for trips in different weather scenarios

Figure 16: Distribution of worthwhileness ratings for trip legs in different weather scenarios

Figure 15 above illustrates the distribution of mood ratings for 7 weather scenarios under different weather conditions as those specified earlier in this section and Figure 16 illustrates the distribution of worthwhileness ratings for the same 7 weather scenarios. The distribution of mood and worthwhileness rating shown at the two graphs follows the overall trend observed in the dataset which located the majority of both mood and worthwhileness ratings between 3 and 5 as shown in [Section 4.3](#) and later at *H1-Q1* within [Section 5.2.3](#). At the same time, mood and worthwhileness distribution across different weather scenarios present similar patterns since the overall distribution of mood for all trip legs is similar to the one with worthwhileness ratings. Further details on the definition and app questions on mood and worthwhileness are presented in [Section 4.2](#).

Figures 15 and 16 above show that weather scenarios formulated based on the temperature, which are Cold, Warm and Uncomfortable Temperature scenarios, present similar distribution of worthwhileness and mood ratings which indicates that there isn't any significant difference among cold and very cold or warm and very warm weather when evaluating travel time. The Neutral/Good together with the Rainy/Snowy weather scenarios present the most notable difference for trip legs that received the highest value of worthwhileness and mood scores of 5, which are around 40% and 50% of trip legs respectively. At the same time, when weather was rainy or snowy, trip legs with a worthwhileness or mood value of 3 (the lowest in the most frequent observed range) were slightly more, indicating that this weather condition might have at the same time a negative impact. Travel behaviour changes in different weather conditions, and the perceived value of travel time is influenced by the different modes of transport chosen.

H15-Q14 What is the distribution of transport modes and worthwhileness ratings among different weather scenarios?

Further to *H15-Q13* above, this research question explores how different weather scenarios associate with modal choice and worthwhileness ratings. Figures 17-21 below illustrate the distribution of relative counts of trip legs (y axis) performed by all five transport mode categories across worthwhileness ratings (x axis) in different weather scenarios.

A similar analysis accounting for absolute instead of relative counts is presented for all transport mode categories within [Appendix 2](#). In summary, these results demonstrate that the majority of trip legs took place in Cloudy and Cold weather scenarios in all different transport mode categories. In addition, Windy weather scenario has a relatively high number of trip legs performed by Public Transport Long

Distance and Neutral/Good weather scenario presented a fair amount of trip legs within Public Transport Short Distance and Cycling & Emerging Micromobility categories. It is noted that these results also reflect the weather conditions at the countries where data was collected from May till mid-December.

The relative counts presented in Figures 17-21 below, can provide a better overview on how weather influences worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios across different mode categories. Relative counts refer to the percentage of different values within only one category, in this case the distribution of worthwhileness ratings within each weather scenario. This means that the sum of all relative counts in one weather scenario add up to 1 or 100 when converted to a percentage.

It is notable that Rainy/Snowy weather scenario presents higher concentration of values closer to 5 in all transport mode categories compared to all other weather scenarios. It is also observed that Windy weather scenario presents more worthwhileness ratings of 1 or 2 in both Public Transport mode categories whereas the distribution of worthwhileness ratings in this scenario seem unaffected in Walking and Private Motorised categories (in comparison with the overall distribution as presented in Figure 4 within [Section 4.3](#)). A more even distribution of worthwhileness ratings is observed in Cold weather scenario across all mode categories apart from Cycling & Emerging Micromobility and Private Motorised, indicating that these weather conditions affect the perceived value of time when walking or using public transport modes. The Neutral/Good weather scenario presents the most unaffected distribution of worthwhileness ratings, meaning that it stays similar to the distribution observed for all trip legs prior to any filtering of data across all transport mode categories as shown in Figure 4 within [Section 4.3](#).

Figure 17: Distribution of relative counts of trip legs performed by Walking modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 18: Distribution of relative counts of trip legs performed by Cycling & Emerging Micromobility modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Overall, public transport modes seem to be more sensitive to weather conditions (Figure 19 and Figure 20) since the overall distribution of worthwhileness ratings is affected the most, with increased lower values of worthwhileness ratings. An exception to that is the Neutral/Good weather scenario where distribution remains unaffected as previously mentioned. It is also observed that worthwhileness ratings in Cycling & Emerging Micromobility are affected most by Uncomfortable Temperature weather scenario, which is uncomfortably warm or cold temperatures. Private Motorised modes seem to be more sensitive to any weather scenario relates to temperature, which are Cold, Warm and Uncomfortable Temperature scenarios. Finally, Walking modes present the most unaffected distribution of worthwhileness ratings compared to other transport mode categories.

Figure 19: Distribution of relative counts of trip legs performed by Public Transport Short Distance modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 20: Distribution of relative counts of trip legs performed by Public Transport Long Distance modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 21: Distribution of relative counts of trip legs performed by Private Motorised modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

5.2.2 ICT analysis

As shown at Table 2 in [Section 3.2.2](#) of this report, there is a number of different research questions related to ICT which are presented below together with the findings and interpretation. In particular, the effects of ICT-related activities (Browsing or social media, Listening to audio, Watching video or gaming and Reading / writing on electronic devices) and ICT-related factors (Internet Connectivity and Charging Opportunity) on users’ travel time worthwhileness will be analysed.

H13-Q1 What are the ICT activities that are more frequently associated with worthwhileness ratings?

To answer this question, it was necessary to analyse the user-identified value resulting from the assessed part of the trip and the ICT-related activities that contributed to the creation of this value. Users identified value of a certain trip leg by answering a question in the Woorti app: “What

value did you take from your time on this trip?”. Users were able to assign ratings (none - 0, some - 1, high - 2) to worthwhileness factors such as paid work, personal tasks, enjoyment and fitness. Subsequently, users were asked which activities contributed to the creation of this value by the question “What exactly did you value doing?”. Only ICT activities were selected for the purpose of answering the hypothesis H13.

The numbers of ICT activities performed during travel considering the evaluation of worthwhileness factors are shown in Figure 22. Regarding ICT activities people listen to audio and browse the Internet the most while travelling with 3,420 and 1,556 trip legs reporting these activities respectively. These two activities bring to passengers a certain amount of enjoyment (E_1). Listening to audio is also associated with zero productivity value of an evaluated trip. People were most engaged in ICT activities during trips that did not bring them any fitness value (F_0).

Activities vs Worthwhileness factors

Figure 22: A matrix showing the number of ICT activities executed by users during travel based on the level of worthwhileness factors (the x-axis shows values of enjoyment (E), fitness (F) and productivity (P))

Figure 23 shows the numbers of ICT activities performed during travel by gender. No significant difference was identified between the activities performed by men and women and their assessment of worthwhileness factors.

Figure 23: Matrixes showing the number of ICT activities executed by users during travel based on the level of worthwhileness factors by gender (the x-axis shows values of enjoyment (E), fitness (F) and productivity (P)).

The assessment of worthwhileness factors and their correlations with ICT activities were also analysed according to the means of transport category (walking, long-distance public transport, short-distance public transport, cycling and emerging micromobility, and private motorised) (Figure 24).

As can be seen in Figure 24, people prefer to listen to audio during active travel. It brings them some form of enjoyment and it is not related to fulfilling work tasks, which is also confirmed by the high frequency of listening at zero productivity. Listening is also characteristic for the private motorised category which is related to the fact that this category mainly includes drivers who must drive the car and thus cannot browse or watch movies, videos. In the case of public transport, passengers are mainly browsing or listening while travelling, which may be due to the availability of Wi-Fi in the means of transport. The highest frequencies of ICT activities were identified at zero fitness factor, which is probably related to a category of means of transport such as public transport. Browsing and listening activities partly affect respondents' value in terms of enjoyment and productivity.

Figure 24: Matrixes showing the number of ICT activities executed by users during travel based on the level of worthwhileness factors by travel mode category (the x-axis shows values of enjoyment (E), fitness (F) and productivity (P))

H13-Q2 What is the correlation between worthwhileness and ICT activities?

This question is focused on identifying the correlation between the evaluation of travel time worthwhileness and ICT activities. Worthwhileness of travel time was measured by the question “Was your travel time wasted or worthwhile?”. Passengers could evaluate their travel time on a 5-point scale in which point 1 meant "All time was wasted" and point 5 meant "All time was worthwhile".

Figure 25 shows a comparison of average worthwhileness rating related to ICT activities for all respondents and by gender. As can be seen, people reading on electronic devices while travelling evaluate their travel time as the most worthwhile. On the contrary, the lowest average value of worthwhileness was identified by people who were browsing while travelling. When comparing the results based on gender, in the case of reading on electronic devices there is a significant difference in evaluating worthwhileness. For men reading on electronic devices, the average worthwhileness value is more than 4.1, while for women it is around 3.8. Differences were also identified in browsing. Men

who browsed the Internet while travelling rated travel time as more worthwhile than women, and vice versa, men who watched videos or movies while travelling considered their travel time less worthwhile than women.

Figure 25: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT activities for all respondents and by gender

Correlation between worthwhileness rating and ICT activities were also analysed based on the category of travel mode (Figure 25). In the case of walking, the average rating of worthwhileness of travel time is higher when listening to music than when browsing the Internet, which is likely due to the very nature of walking. These two activities were also analysed for the category of cycling and emerging micromobility. In this category, people who browsed the Internet while travelling considered their travel time more worthwhile than those who listened to audio. This is very interesting as it is not possible to browse the Internet while cycling or riding an e-scooter. This finding may be caused by browsing during certain stops, or the evaluation of the travel time worthwhileness is not directly influenced by this ICT activity but by other activities or experience factors.

Figure 26: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT activities by category of travel mode

Average values of travel time worthwhileness for ICT activities are partly similar for long-distance public transport and short-distance public transport. People find their travel time more worthwhile when reading electronic devices while travelling. On the other hand, the lowest values of worthwhileness were found when people browsed the internet while travelling by short-distance public transport and when they watched videos or movies while travelling by long-distance public transport. This may indicate that these activities are done just to make perceived travel time shorter (i.e. in other words, people chose to “kill time”). An interesting finding for the private motorised travel modes category is the high average rating of worthwhileness for reading on electronic devices. However, this finding can only be linked to passengers, as drivers cannot read during driving.

Figure 27: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT activities by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

The evaluation of travel time worthwhileness and its correlation with ICT activities was also analysed from a national perspective. For Finland, Slovakia, Croatia and Spain, there are no significant differences in the average rating of travel time worthwhileness and individual ICT activities. In other countries, ICT activities that have average worthwhileness rating significantly higher or lower than other ICT activities are identified. These results are shown in Figure 27 where all ICT-related activities

are illustrated (Browsing or social media (B), Listening to audio (L), Reading / writing on electronic devices (R) and Watching video or gaming (W)) together with the corresponding values of average worthwhileness ratings across countries.

H13-Q3 What is the role of ICT in shaping VTT: how are the two factors “Internet connectivity” and “Charging opportunity” correlated to travel worthwhileness?

This question examines the correlation between worthwhileness of travel time and ICT-related experience factors. The worthwhileness of travel time was measured as described in the previous question using a 5-point scale in which respondents chose whether their time was wasted or worthwhile. Charging opportunity and Internet connectivity belong to a set of 48 experience factors¹⁵, for which users could report their contribution to the perceived quality of travel time. Charging opportunity was available only for transport modes which are included in the categories of public transport and private motorised. This experience factor was evaluated in 2,881 legs. Internet connectivity was available only in the public transport category and it was evaluated in 1,380 legs.

Figure 28 shows the correlation between average worthwhileness rating and ICT experience factors for all users, by gender and transport category. The average worthwhileness rating is almost the same for both factors when answers from all users are analysed. Gender comparison shows that men who consider internet connectivity to be an important factor while travelling evaluate their travel time more positively than women. This is also the case with the charging opportunity factor, but the difference between men and women is less significant.

Figure 28: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and charging opportunity and internet connectivity by gender and transport category.

Considering the category of mode of transport, the correlation between the evaluation of travel time worthwhileness and internet connectivity is not different for short-distance public transport and long-distance public transport. Considering long-distance public transport, Internet connectivity was reported among the top 10 most frequent experience factors. Internet connectivity was not an available factor in other mode categories. Comparing average worthwhileness rating for charging opportunity, the highest values are reported in long-distance public transport and private motorised

¹⁵ Some of the experience factors were only relevant for specific modes of transport.

modes of transport. This may be related to the easy availability of charging, whether in a car or long-distance mode of transport.

Correlation between worthwhileness rating and ICT experience factors were also analysed by country (Figure 29). Based on these results, countries can be divided 3 categories: countries in which the average worthwhileness rating is higher in the case of charging opportunities (Croatia, Portugal, and Slovakia), countries in which the average rating is higher for the internet connectivity (Belgium, Finland, Italy, and Norway) and countries in which the average values are similar (Spain and France). Travellers in the first country category considered their travel time more worthwhile when they picked charging opportunity as an experience factor whilst travellers from the second category considered their travel time more worthwhile when they picked Internet connectivity.

Figure 29: Correlation between average worthwhileness rating and charging opportunity and internet connectivity by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain).

5.2.3 Transport infrastructure and services

As shown at Table 3 earlier at [Section 3.2.3](#) of this report, there is a number of different research questions related to transport infrastructure and services which are presented below together with the findings and interpretation.

H1-Q1 Is there a correlation between number of legs and the mood within a trip?

To analyse this question all trips with a maximum of 10 trip legs were included whereas waiting events were excluded from the calculations. It is noted that mood is reflected by the response to the following question in Woorti app: "Overall, how did you feel about this trip?", which is the first question asked to users validating a trip who could report between 1 to 5 stars indicating a lousy to a great mood.

Box plots at Figure 28 below illustrate the median, lower and upper quartiles of mood scoring across different number of legs within a trip for all users, male and female. The plots do not show any correlation between the number of trip legs and the mood with no significant difference among female and male users.

The average score of mood reported from all users was around 4 out of 5 and most values were within the range of 3-5. This trend does not change when observing the same mood score values in trips with different number of legs. The analysis was also performed across different countries and age groups

however no significant differences were found on the number of trip legs and the mood score travellers reported for the trip. These plots can be found in [Appendix 3](#).

Figure 30: Box plots illustrating the median, lower and upper quartiles of mood scoring across different number of trip legs within a trip by gender

H1-Q2 Is there a correlation between trip duration, duration of transfers (i.e. waiting time) and the mood?

The graphs below illustrate the average duration of trip legs and waiting events in minutes for all different values of mood reported for a trip. Figure 31 shows the difference between male and female users and Figure 32 illustrates results across different countries. It is noted that the majority of mood scores were between 3 and 5 so the interpretation of the graph for mood scores close to 1 and 2 should be done carefully due to the limited amount of data.

As anticipated, the average duration of waiting events is lower compared to the duration of trip legs. It is also observed that different duration levels are assigned different mood scores but without any similar pattern among different genders or different countries. Patterns differ significantly among countries whereas there is no outstanding difference among male and female users. Therefore, it is concluded that there is no correlation between trip duration, waiting events and the mood score users assigned to the trip.

Figure 31: Mood scoring and average duration of trip legs and waiting events by gender

Figure 32: Mood scoring and average duration of trip legs and waiting events by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

H1-Q5 Which types of transfer are more significant in terms of high or low levels of mood?

For the lowest and highest values of mood, which are 1 star and 5 stars respectively, it is sought which are the most common types of transfer between modes of transport. It is noted that data is limited for the lowest possible score for mood since most users rated a trip from 3 to 5. Therefore, the frequency of transfer types is also significantly lower as shown at Table 15.

The tables below show the most frequent transfer types for the lowest (Table 15) and highest (Table 16) levels of mood reported by users. For mood ratings equal to 1 the most common type of transfer is between walking and car driving and between walking and riding a bus. The combination of walking and train or subway or tram were also rated with the lowest mood score, with either mode of transport being first.

Transfer type when mood scored lowest (1)	Number of transfers
walking → carDriver	276
bus → walking	262
carDriver → walking	258
walking → bus	252
train → walking	84
walking → train	73
walking → subway	70
subway → walking	65
tram → walking	47
walking → tram	38

Table 15: Most frequent transfer types when users reported mood 1 for trips

For trip mood ratings equal to 5, which is the highest possible score, the most common type of transfer is again between walking and car driving and between walking and riding a bus, similar to when trips were rated with the lowest mood score of 1. The highest mood rating was also reported for transfers between walking and subway or train. The type of transfer which was not present at previous Table 15, is between walking and bicycle.

It is notable that the most frequent types of transfer always incorporate “walking” as one of the two trip legs. It is worth mentioning that walking might be either part of the transfer or a trip itself.

Transfer type when mood scored lowest (1)	Number of transfers
walking → carDriver	1812
carDriver → walking	1541
bus → walking	1154
walking → bus	1092
walking → bicycle	663
bicycle → walking	659
train → walking	591
walking → train	539
subway → walking	503
walking → subway	473

Table 16: Most frequent transfer types when users reported mood 5 for trips

H2-Q1 How is the reliability of travel time related to worthwhile assessments?

This question is analysed by distributing all 5 values of worthwhileness for those trip legs that “reliability” was rated positively or negatively by users when assessing the quality of travel time. Worthwhileness ratings range from wasted time to worthwhile time and they were values assigned to trip legs by users as part of a trip validation. It is noted that all graphs below present worthwhileness ratings from 1 to 5 at the x axis and the frequency of reliability reported as a negative or positive factor of a trip leg on the y axis from a scale 0 to 1 denoting a percentage.

Figure 33 shows how reliability was chosen as a positive or negative factor across different values of worthwhileness by gender. It is generally observed that the higher the worthwhileness rating the most frequent is the selection of reliability as a positive factor affecting quality of travel time. Moreover, the graph shows that approximately 40% of the trip legs where reliability had a positive impact were given the best evaluation in terms of worthwhileness. This indicates that reliability can play an important role in a positive travel experience. The cases where reliability was reported to have a negative impact on the quality of travel time, were more evenly distributed across different values of worthwhileness ratings from 1 to 5. This pattern is still present in male and female users, however, is more evident between male users.

Figure 33: Reliability as a positive and negative factor across different worthwhileness values by gender

When reliability and worthwhileness ratings are compared across different modes of transport, Figure 34 shows that the pattern observed above in all users is quite different depending on the mode. For example, in Cycling and Emerging Micromobility as well as Walking categories, reliability as a negative factor is increasingly selected when worthwhileness values increase. One explanation could be that when users perceived a trip as worthwhile, they were comparing reliability with alternative modes of transport where travel time is not so predictable as with walking and cycling. In public transport modes and private motorised, the distribution of reliability as a positive and negative factor is more even across different values of worthwhileness, indicating that this factor influences the perceived value of travel time in these mode categories since the distribution differs significantly compared to the overall distribution of worthwhileness ratings (Figure 4 in [Section 4.3](#)).

Figure 35 below shows a comparison of reliability and worthwhileness ratings across different trip purposes. The general pattern observed for all users is also observed for different trip purposes. Reliability is selected as a positive factor more frequently for trip legs that received higher score in worthwhileness ratings. On the other hand, reliability is selected as a negative factor at similar frequencies across different values of worthwhileness. An exemption to that pattern is observed for ‘Everyday Shopping’ where positive and negative selections of reliability presented more similar frequencies across different values of worthwhileness. Interestingly, reliability is more frequently reported as a positive factor for the maximum worthwhileness value of 5 in ‘Leisure’ or ‘Everyday Shopping’ trips compared to trips to ‘Work’ or ‘Home’.

An analysis was performed across different countries where different patterns were observed as shown in Figure 56 included in [Appendix 4](#). In addition, Figure 57 in [Appendix 4](#) shows a comparison between a weekday and a weekend which presents very similar behaviour.

Figure 34: Reliability as a positive and negative factor across different worthwhileness values by transport mode category

Figure 35: Reliability as a positive and negative factor across different worthwhileness values by trip purpose

H9-Q3 What are the negative experience factors for trip legs performed by alternative modes for users of motorised transport?

The aim of this question is to explore the potential of users of Private Motorised modes to shift to other modes of transport. All modes of the Private Motorised category are described in [Section 5.1](#) of this report. To analyse this question, the following steps of data filtering were followed:

1. Selection of trip legs performed by Private Motorised modes;
2. From this dataset, selection of users that have validated at least one trip leg;
3. Among users from the previous step, the ones with at least one preferred transport mode category among "Cycling & Emerging Micromobility" and "Public Transport Short Distance" are selected, and;
4. From users resulting from the previous step, the top negative experience factors were extracted for all trips that were not performed by Private Motorised modes.

Table 17 below shows the top 10 experience factors that users of Private Motorised modes reported to negatively affect their perceived value of travel time when performing trip legs with alternative modes of transport either within Cycling & Emerging Micromobility or Public Transport Short Distance category. The overall negative experience factors reported by all users, are presented at Table 19 in the following question H15-Q1. In comparison to this overall trend, Table 17 below highlights those factors that didn't appear in the top 10 negative experience factors for all users, indicating with darker colour those factors that were not in the top 20 experience factors either.

Experience factor in Cycling & Emerging Micromobility trip legs	Proportion in mode category	Experience factor in Public Transport Short Distance trip legs	Proportion in mode category
Cars/Other Vehicles	14%	Privacy	7%
Air Quality	10%	Crowdedness/Seating	7%
Road/Path Availability and Safety	10%	Other People	7%
Noise Level	9%	Seating Quality/Personal Space	7%
Road/Path Quality	8%	Noise Level	6%
Traffic Signals/Crossings	7%	Internet Connectivity	6%
Crowding/Congestion	7%	Charging Opportunity	6%
Today's Weather	5%	Air Quality	5%
Simplicity/Difficulty of the Route	3%	Scenery	5%
Facilities (showers, lockers)	3%	Reliability of Travel Time	4%

Table 17: Top 10 negative experience factors reported for alternative modes among users of Private Motorised modes

For trip legs in Cycling & Emerging Micromobility, Noise Level and Today's Weather were selected in lower frequency in comparison to what all users have reported, indicating that these experience factors have less importance in shaping negatively the perceived value of travel time. At the same time, three additional experience factors are now within the top 10 factors which are Traffic Signals/Crossings, Simplicity/Difficulty of the Route and Facilities (showers, lockers). Cars/Other vehicles is by far the most frequent factor reported by users of Private Motorised modes, reflecting safety concerns.

Interestingly, in Public Transport Short Distance trip legs more than half of the top 10 negative experience factors were not present in the respective top 10 factors reported by all users. In addition, Seating Quality/Personal Space and Internet Connectivity were not reported even among the top 20 experience factors negatively affecting the perceived value of travel time. Privacy has now the first

place whereas Crowdedness/Seating, Other People and Charging Opportunity moved more than 6 places higher in the list compared to the list with the negative experience factors reported by all users. At the same time, Noise Level (like in Cycling & Emerging Micromobility), Air Quality and Scenery received less importance by users of Private Motorised modes evaluating their perceived value of travel time when performing trip legs by Public Transport Short Distance modes.

The Ability to do What I Wanted is the only experience factor that was not among the top 10 negative factors for alternative trip legs performed by users of Private Motorised modes although it was reported among the top 10 for all users as shown in Table 19.

These findings can provide insights towards which are the areas of improvement that can lead to increased levels of satisfaction for trips within Cycling & Emerging Micromobility and Public Transport Short Distance potentially shifting car drivers travel behaviour.

H15-Q1 What are the top positive and negative experience factors?

The Woorti app had a total of 48 different experience factors for which users could report a positive or negative contribution to the perceived quality of travel time. The tables below illustrate the top 20 most frequently selected experience factors contributing positively or negatively in the journey experience, together with the number of trip legs for which they were selected. Some of the experience factors were only relevant for specific modes of transport which is outlined in the second column of the tables. The experience factors that are not highlighted are common in both tables. The top 10 most frequently selected experience factors contributing positively or negatively in the journey experience is presented for all transport mode categories within [Appendix 5](#).

The full list of experience factors across the different transport mode categories can be found in [Section 5.1](#) of this report. It should be noted that for all trip legs where experience factors were selected by users, the majority was referred to experience factors having a positive influence on the quality of travel time representing around 79% of the total responses. For the interpretation of the results in this section, it is recommended to consider at the same time the frequency of modes of transport in validated trip legs which as shown in Figure 6 within [Section 4.3](#).

Overall, it is observed that 14 out of 20 most frequently reported experience factors are present at both positive and negative evaluations however with more trip legs having positive evaluations as mentioned earlier. Among those common factors, those relevant for all modes of transport are today's weather, reliability, simplicity/difficulty of the route, scenery, ability to do what I wanted, noise level, air quality, information and signs, and the ability to take kids or pets along. It is noteworthy that many unusual experience factors, compared to conventional planning, rated high in both negative and positive evaluations of perceived value of travel time such as 'Ability to do what I wanted', 'Scenery' or 'Other people'. At the same time, 'Internet Connectivity' was not observed among the top 20 experience factors reported by users which might be due to the fact that Public Transport trip legs, for which this factor was available, were not as many.

Table 18 below presents the top 20 experience factors that reported to have a positive contribution to the perceived value of travel time. It is observed that quite a few of them relate to transport services and infrastructure such as the road path availability, quality and directness, reliability, parking, information and signs or route planning and navigation tools. It is worth mentioning that 'Simplicity/Difficulty of the Route' was the top experience factor which affected positively the

perceived value of travel time in 12.7% of trip legs. 'Today's weather' and 'Ability to do what I want' were also reported as positive experience factors in a significant amount of trip legs.

Positive factors	Modes for which experience factor was available	Number of trip legs	Proportion of total trip legs
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	all	19,507	12.7%
Todays_Weather	all	15,635	10.2%
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	all	12,638	8.2%
Scenery	all	10,822	7.0%
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	all	9,367	6.1%
Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	Active modes	7,441	4.8%
Road_Path_Directness	Active modes	6,437	4.2%
Road_Path_Quality	Active & Private motorised	6,277	4.1%
Noise_Level	all	5,550	3.6%
Parking_At_End_Points	Cycling & Private motorised	5,439	3.5%
Air_Quality	all	5,185	3.4%
Security_And_Safety	PT & Private motorised	5,092	3.3%
Other_People	PT & Active modes	4,907	3.2%
Route_Planning_Navigation_Tools	all	4,566	3.0%
Information_And_Signs	all	4,481	2.9%
Ability_To_Take_Kids_Or_Pets_Along	all	4,089	2.7%
Convenient_Access	PT	4,026	2.6%
Vehicle_Quality	Private motorised	3,985	2.6%
Lighting_Visibility	Active modes	3,832	2.5%
Privacy	PT & Private motorised	3,572	2.3%

Table 18: Top 20 positive experience factors reported by users (highlighted are the experience factors that were not present in top 20 negative factors)

Table 19 below presents the top 20 experience factors travellers reported to have a negative contribution to the perceived value of travel time. An additional feature presented at this table is the indication of unwanted efforts next to each experience factor that was rated negatively. Unwanted efforts are external stressors that prevent engaging into worthwhile activities and can be categorised as follows:

- Physical (p) is an effort asked of and imposed on the body in undertaking travel such as having to stand in a crowded bus or go upstairs;
- Cognitive (c) effort is the mental focus that is needed to execute the journey successfully e.g. noisy or attention demanding environment (unwanted distractions, difficulty to plan trip or know where to go), and;
- Affective (a) is the emotional influence of undertaking the journey i.e. stressful, unsafe or unreliable.

Negative Factors (& Category of Unwanted Efforts)	Modes for which experience factor was available	Number of trip legs	Proportion of total trip legs
Noise_Level (c)	all	3,726	2.4%
Air_Quality (a)	all	3,423	2.2%
Cars_Other_Vehicles (c)	Active & Private motorised	3,367	2.2%
Todays_Weather (a)	all	3,078	2.0%
Scenery (a)	all	2,426	1.6%
Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety (a)	Active modes	1,989	1.3%
Road_Path_Quality (c)	Active & Private motorised	1,962	1.3%
Crowding_Congestion (p)	Active modes	1,782	1.2%
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted (c)	all	1,699	1.1%

Traffic_Congestion_Delays (a)	Private motorised	1,668	1.1%
Other_People (c)	PT & Active modes	1,610	1.0%
Traffic_Signals_Crossings (a)	Active modes	1,608	1.0%
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route (c)	all	1,571	1.0%
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time (a)	all	1,315	0.9%
Ability_To_Take_Kids_Or_Pets_Along (p)	all	1,237	0.8%
Facilities_Shower_Lockers (a)	Active modes	1,225	0.8%
Charging_Opportunity (a)	PT & Private motorised	1,074	0.7%
Convenient_Access (p)	PT	999	0.7%
Information_And_Signs (c)	all	984	0.6%
Privacy (c)	PT & Private motorised	952	0.6%

Table 19: Top 20 negative experience factors reported by users *(unwanted efforts): a stands for affective c for cognitive and p for physical (highlighted are the experience factors that were not present in top 20 positive factors)

Identifying the unwanted efforts travellers must make during a trip leg, can indicate which interventions are more relevant to apply for improving the journey experience. However, this would require a more detailed assessment and data analysis, looking into specific modes or cities where users reported negative experience factors.

H15-Q3 What is the distribution of top satisfaction/dissatisfaction factors related to “Crowdedness and Seating availability” in public transport modes?

This research question explores how crowdedness and seating availability impacts satisfaction levels as a proxy for the comfort of travelling with public transport. Those two variables were merged into one experience factor which was only available for the validation of trip legs completed with modes of public transport.

Figure 36 below illustrates the trip legs for which “Crowdedness_Seating” experience factor was selected as a positive or negative contributor (y axis) to the value of travel time across all modes of public transport (x axis) for all users, male and female. All graphs indicate that crowdedness and seating availability was mostly reported to have a positive impact on the value of travel time. It is shown that “Crowdedness_Seating” was more frequently selected for bus journeys followed by train and subway trip legs. However, this might be related to the frequency of trip legs across transport modes i.e. bus journeys are more compared to train or tram journeys.

Figure 36: Counts of crowdedness and seating availability as a positive and negative experience in public transport modes by gender

To be able to compare the frequency of crowdedness and seating availability across modes, the relative counts of the same factor within each mode of public transport are shown in Figure 37 below. Similar to Figure 36 above, crowdedness and seating availability was mostly reported to have a positive impact on the value of travel time. It is now shown that travellers tend to give more importance to “Crowdedness_Seating” when journeys with public transport are longer, with long distance bus, high speed and intercity train trip legs presenting higher relative counts. In particular, almost 20% of trip legs performed by bus for long distance reported “Crowdedness_Seating” to have a positive influence in the perceived value of travel time. It is also noted that this experience factor is more important for high speed and intercity train trip legs among male users of the app rather than long bus journeys which remains the first mode for female users.

Figure 37: Relative counts of crowdedness and seating availability as a positive and negative experience in public transport modes by gender

Figure 38: Counts of crowdedness and seating availability as a positive and negative experience in public transport modes by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

The preferences in terms of the importance of “Crowdedness_Seating” among different public transport modes varies significantly across countries as shown in Figure 36. A bus journey is still the

first mode that users perceive “Crowdedness_Seating” to have importance across 6 countries, however it is observed that intercity train trips are by far the most important in terms of crowdedness and seating availability in Belgium, equally important in Norway while ferry trips arrive in the second place in Portugal. In some countries it is also now shown that “Crowdedness_Seating” received more negative evaluation than positive for some modes of transport, such as in Croatia, Italy and Spain.

It is worth mentioning that although “Crowdedness_Seating” is not among the top 20 most frequently selected experience factors (as shown in Tables 18 and 19 of H15-Q1 section), it was among the top 5 experience factors selected in trip legs performed by public transport modes as illustrated at Table 20 below.

All public transport	Number of trip legs
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	2732
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	2689
Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	2199
Crowdedness_Seating	2178
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	2175
Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	2085
Scenery	1888
Security_And_Safety	1772

Table 20: Top 10 experience factors selected in all public transport modes

H15-Q7 What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and satisfaction factors?

This question examines the correlation of experience factors and worthwhileness values for both positive and negative selections. The analysis is performed by gender, country and transport mode category. Figure 39 considers only trip legs for which positive experience factors were selected from the users. It is noted that a trip leg with positive experience factors might have also negative experience factors reported at the same time. The histogram clearly demonstrates a higher frequency of trip legs with positive experience factors for higher values of worthwhileness. The same trend is also observed among female and male users.

Figure 39: Worthwhileness ratings for trip legs with positive experience factors selected by all users (left), by gender (right)

Figure 40 below shows the distribution of worthwhileness values for all trip legs that negative experience factors were selected by the users. It is noted that trip legs rated between 3 and 5 in terms of their worthwhile travel time, were assigned similar amount of negative experience factors. It is observed that female users were reporting fewer negative factors when the trip was more worthwhile (for ratings 3 to 5) while this relation was opposite for male users.

Figure 40: Worthwhileness ratings for trip legs with negative experience factors selected by all users (left), by gender (right)

The analysis that follows demonstrates the average worthwhileness ratings across different countries and different transport mode categories. Figure 41 includes only trip legs with positive experience factors and Figure 42 shows trip legs that received negative experience factors. Firstly, it is observed that the average worthwhileness for trip legs where positive experience factors were reported is higher compared to trip legs where negative experience factors were reported. Regarding transport mode categories, in both cases cycling and walking trip legs were rated higher in terms of their worthwhileness. In the case of trip legs with negative experience factors (Figure 40), the worthwhileness rating for long distance public transport didn't drop as much as it did for private modes and short distance public transport. One explanation might be that long distance public transport modes had a more balanced distribution of negative and positive experience factors.

Figure 41: Average worthwhileness values for trip legs with positive experience factors selected by users, by country (left) and by transport category (right)

Figure 42: Average worthwhileness values for trip legs with negative experience factors selected by users, by country (left) (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain) and by transport category (right)

In conclusion, worthwhileness ratings do not seem to be strongly correlated to negative experience factors as those reported by users. However, positive experience factors are found more frequently in higher ratings of worthwhileness. This might be due to the fact that trip legs with negative experience factors were significantly lower compared to positive ones representing 21% of the total trip legs with experience factors assigned. Therefore, the influence of negative experience factors, if any, would be harder to identify.

H15-Q9 What is the correlation between worthwhileness assessments and satisfaction factors and activities?

This question aims to explore if there is any correlation of activities with satisfaction levels of experience factors and worthwhileness values. In particular, it is sought if any specific combination of experience factors and activities is associated with particularly high or low worthwhileness assessments. For this purpose, the data is presented for the 2 end values of worthwhileness which are 1 (lowest) and 5 (highest). At the same time, experience factors rated negatively and positively are investigated separately.

Figure 43: Combination of experience factors rated positively (y axis) and activities (x axis) for trip legs with the lowest worthwhileness value of 1

Figure 43 above illustrates a heatmap with the number of trip legs that received a worthwhileness rating of 1 with different combinations of positively rated experience factors (y axis) and activities (x axis). Figure 44 below presents the same data but for experience factors that were rated negatively. Interestingly, even though trip legs were rated with the lowest worthwhileness value of 1, positively rated experience factors seem to be reported more frequently compared to those received a negative perceived value of travel time which also reflects the higher frequency of trip legs with positive experience factors assigned.

Figure 44: Combination of experience factors rated negatively (y axis) and activities (x axis) for trip legs with the lowest worthwhileness value of 1

The most frequently reported combinations of activities and experience factors when those rated positively in trip legs with a worthwhileness rating of 1 (Figure 43) are Simplicity/Difficulty of the route while Talking or while Listening to audio and Today's weather while Thinking. When experience factors were rated negatively for the same trip legs with worthwhileness value of 1 (Figure 44), the most common combinations of activities and factors are Ability to do what I wanted while Thinking, Traffic Congestion/Delays and Reliability of travel time while Listening to audio and Noise level while Thinking.

Figure 45 illustrates the number of trip legs that received a worthwhileness rating of 5 with different combinations of positively rated experience factors (y axis) and activities (x axis) and Figure 46 presents the same data but for experience factors that were rated negatively. It is observed that the frequency of trip legs is much higher compared to the previous 2 graphs, which reflects the general pattern of data which is concentrated between worthwhileness values of 3 and 5. Similar to the previous Figures 43 and 44 with worthwhileness ratings of 1, positively rated experience factors were reported with a higher frequency (Figure 45) compared to negatively rated factors (Figure 46), which is now in alignment with the highest value of worthwhileness assigned to these trip legs.

Figure 45: Combination of experience factors rated positively (y axis) and activities (x axis) for trip legs with the highest worthwhileness value of 5

The most frequently reported combinations of activities and experience factors when those rated positively in trip legs with a worthwhileness rating of 5 (Figure 45) are Simplicity/Difficulty of the route while Accompanying someone or Thinking and Ability to do what I wanted while Accompanying someone or Thinking. For the same trip legs but with negative experience factors assigned to them (Figure 46), the most frequent combinations of activities and factors are reported while performing the activity of Cycling in combination with the experience factors of Cars/Other vehicles, Road path availability and safety, Noise levels and Road path quality.

Figure 46: Combination of experience factors rated negatively (y axis) and activities (x axis) for trip legs with the highest worthwhileness value of 5

It is noted that when experience factors were rated positively, Simplicity/Difficulty of the route was among the most frequent combinations in both low and high worthwhileness ratings, however with different activities assigned; Talking or Listening to audio were present in low worthwhileness ratings and Accompanying someone or Thinking were in high worthwhileness ratings. The high frequency of Simplicity/Difficulty of the route experience factor is in alignment with the findings of H15-Q1 which showed that this factor was the most reported. It is interesting though how different activities were carried out in different perceptions of value of travel time.

The combination of experience factors and activities reported in all Figures 43-46 differs significantly. At the same time, the frequency of the reported values for trip legs shown in the heatmaps reflect the general patterns of the respective values observed in the dataset (i.e. most frequently selected experience factors and activities are also shown here) which should be taken into account when interpreting the results.

H16-Q1 How are experience factors related to “Smoothness” correlated to worthwhileness?

Smoothness as an experience factor is represented by “Road path quality” and “Road path directness” in active transport, “Vehicle ride smoothness” in public transport and “Road quality/Vehicle ride smoothness” in private motorised modes.

Figure 47 below shows the average worthwhileness values (y axis) for trip legs that experience factors related to smoothness (x axis) were rated positively (left graph) and negatively (right graph). Both graphs in Figure 47 also illustrate the values for female and male genders. Overall it is shown that male users present higher worthwhileness values in all smoothness factors apart from the “Vehicle ride smoothness”. Moreover, when smoothness factors were reported to have a negative contribution to the perceived value of travel time, the worthwhileness value for the trip leg was also lower in all smoothness factors. That might indicate that smoothness plays an important role in shaping the journey experience. It is also observed that when negatively rated smoothness factors were selected for active modes, the trip legs received higher worthwhileness ratings compared to the two remaining experience factors.

Figure 47: Experience factors related to trip smoothness selected as positive (left) or negative (right) by gender

Figure 48: Experience factors related to trip smoothness selected as positive or negative by country (AAA – other, BEL – Belgium, HRV – Croatia, FIN – Finland, FRA – France, ITA – Italy, NOR – Norway, PRT – Portugal, SVK – Slovakia, ESP – Spain)

Figure 48 above illustrates the average worthwhileness values (y axis) for trip legs that experience factors related to smoothness (x axis) were rated positively (blue dots) and negatively (orange dots) across different countries. The x axis illustrates the same experience factors as in Figure 47 above, which are Road Quality (RQ), Road Directness (RD), Vehicle Smoothness (VS) and Road Smoothness

(RS). For the interpretation of these graphs it is important to consider the distribution of male and female users across countries as shown in Figure 4 in [Section 4.3](#), since higher worthwhileness ratings reported by male users alter the results.

H16-Q2 When factors on smoothness are negatively rated, what are the activities that are carried out while on the move (and how does that compare to “normal” list of activities when this factor is not mentioned)?

This research question complements the previous question *H16-Q1* aiming to explore further which activities are present when experience factors related to “Smoothness” are rated negatively. Furthermore, is being explored how these activities compare in relation to the most frequent ones presented in all trip legs.

Table 21 below presents all 15 activities available in the Woorti app in ascending order based on their frequency of selection without any filter applied (first column) and when smoothness related factors were negatively rated (second column) by gender (last two columns). The full description of activities is available at Table 10 in [Section 5.1](#). Moreover, the table shows those activities available only to non-driving modes with one asterisk (*) and those relevant only to driving modes with two asterisks (**). The driving and non-driving modes can be found in Table 9 within [Section 5.1](#). It is reminded that smoothness as an experience factor is represented by “Road path quality” and “Road path directness” in active modes of transport, “Vehicle ride smoothness” in public transport and “Road quality/Vehicle ride smoothness” in private motorised modes.

Firstly, it is observed that all 15 activities were selected when smoothness was rated negatively however with a different order. These experience factors seem to be more relevant for Cycling, which is the activity that comes first when smoothness is rated negatively. Another activity that was selected more when these experience factors were rated negatively is Personal Care. At the same time, accompanying someone and Relaxing or sleeping are two activities that appeared with less frequency, indicating that these activities are not so relevant for negative experience factors related to smoothness.

Male users have a similar order of activities compared to the total users which is expected since 62% of trip legs were validated by male users. It is worth noting that when female users reported smoothness factors to negatively affect their perceived value of travel time, Thinking was reported in 22% of those trip legs compared to 16% of the same trip legs reported by male users. Thinking activity together with Cycling were the ones with the most notable difference between male and female users.

Order of all activities	Order of all activities when smoothness was negatively rated	Order of all activities when smoothness was negatively rated - Male	Order of all activities when smoothness was negatively rated - Female
Accompanying	Cycling**	Cycling**	Thinking
Thinking	Thinking	Thinking	Cycling**
Talking	Talking	Talking	Accompanying
Walking**	Accompanying	Accompanying	Talking
Cycling**	Walking**	Walking**	Walking**
Listening	Listening	Listening	Listening
Driving**	Browsing	Browsing	Browsing
Browsing	Driving**	Driving**	Other
Eating	Eating	Eating	Driving**
Relaxing*	Personal Care	Personal Care	Eating
Reading (Device)*	Other	Other	Reading (Device)*
Other	Reading (Device)*	Reading (Device)*	Personal Care

Personal Care	Relaxing*	Relaxing*	Reading (Paper)*
Reading (Paper)*	Reading (Paper)*	Watching*	Relaxing*
Watching*	Watching*	Reading (Paper)*	Watching*

*Available only to non-driving modes**Available only to driving modes

Table 21: Sort ascending activities based on their frequency of selection without any filter and when smoothness related factors were negatively rated by gender

5.3 A summary of most significant factors influencing VTT

This section presents the most notable findings in all results of the data analysis presented in this report. In addition to the three dimensions of the analysis (Weather, ICT and Transport Services & Infrastructure), most valuable findings are presented for gender, transport mode categories and mood versus worthwhileness assessments where relevant. These results can potentially guide policies and identify the most appropriate practices for different countries, modes of transport and genders.

Weather conditions

When data was analysed based on 7 **different weather scenarios**, it was shown that travel behaviour was different depending on weather conditions, and the perceived value of travel time was influenced by the different modes of transport chosen. The Neutral/Good together with the Rainy/Snowy weather scenarios present the most notable difference for trip legs that received the highest value of worthwhileness and mood scores of 5, which are around 40% and 50% of trip legs respectively. At the same time, when weather was rainy or snowy, trip legs with a worthwhileness or mood value of 3 (the lowest in the most frequent observed range) were slightly more, indicating that this weather condition might have at the same time a negative impact. Furthermore, weather scenarios formulated based on the temperature, which are Cold, Warm and Uncomfortable Temperature scenarios, presented similar distribution of worthwhileness ratings which indicates that there isn't any significant difference among cold and very cold or warm and very warm weather when evaluating travel time.

Regarding different transport mode categories, **Public Transport modes** seem to be more sensitive to weather conditions with an exception of Neutral/Good weather scenario. Worthwhileness ratings in **Cycling & Emerging Micromobility** are affected most by Uncomfortable Temperature weather scenario, which is uncomfortably warm or cold temperatures. **Private Motorised modes** seem to be more sensitive to any weather scenario relates to temperature and **Walking** modes present the most unaffected distribution of worthwhileness ratings compared to the rest transport mode categories.

Today's Weather was reported among the top 10 most frequent **experience factors** in all transport mode categories apart from Public Transport (PT) used for Short Distance trips a finding in alignment with empirical evidence. The data analysis across mode categories demonstrated that for those **walking, jogging or running**, a negative experience with weather, such as adverse conditions, does not affect an overall worthwhile trip. Regarding the frequency of "Today's weather" as a positive or negative experience factor across worthwhileness values, no significant difference was found among male and female users.

The analysis of weather scenarios across **mood and worthwhileness** ratings presented very similar behaviour which is mainly due to the fact that mood and worthwhileness ratings received similar scoring by the users.

ICT analysis

In the part focused on ICT-related activities and ICT-related experience factors, it was found that listening to audio and browsing the Internet are the most frequent **ICT-related activities** while travelling. However, results show that people who browse the Internet while travelling find their travel time the least worthwhile, and conversely, people who read electronic devices find their travel time the most worthwhile.

The results indicate also differences in the use of ICT and the perception of the value of travel time by **gender**. The worthwhileness of travel time is evaluated more positively by men than women when reading electronic devices or browsing the Internet. Regarding ICT-related experience factors men who consider Internet connectivity to be an important factor while travelling evaluate their travel time more positively than women. On the other hand, regarding the numbers of ICT activities performed during travel by, no significant difference was identified between the activities performed by men and women and their assessment of worthwhileness factors.

Different ICT-related activities and ICT-related experience factors were found also across different transport mode categories. High frequency of listening to audio activity was found among **active modes of transport** at zero levels of productivity. In the case of walking, the average rating of worthwhileness of travel time is higher when listening to music than when browsing the internet, which is likely due to the very nature of walking. On the other hand, users of Cycling & Emerging Micromobility modes considered their travel time more worthwhile when browsing to the internet compared to listening to audio, an activity probably performed in stops.

Listening to audio is also a frequent activity for the **private motorised** category which is related to the fact that this category mainly includes drivers who must drive the car and thus cannot browse or watch movies, videos. An interesting finding for the private motorised travel modes category is the high average rating of worthwhileness for reading on electronic devices which is probably linked to passengers of this mode category.

In the case of **public transport**, passengers are mainly browsing the internet or listening to audio while travelling, which may be due to the availability of Wi-Fi in this means of transport. Average values of travel time worthwhileness for ICT activities are similar for long-distance public transport and short-distance public transport.

Transport services and infrastructure

The analysis performed related to **mood ratings** showed that the average score of mood reported from all users was around 4 out of 5 and most values were within the range of 3-5. In addition, there was no correlation found between the number of trip legs and the mood either between trip duration, waiting events and the mood score users assigned to the trip. Regarding the **type of transfers and the mood ratings** assigned for the whole trip, it was found that the most frequent types of transfer always incorporated “walking” as one of the two trip legs. It is worth mentioning that walking was either part of the transfer or a trip itself.

Data analysis showed that for all trip legs where **experience factors** were selected by users, the majority was referred to experience factors having a positive influence on the quality of travel time representing around 79% of the total responses. Overall, it was observed that 14 out of 20 most frequently reported experience factors were present at both positive and negative evaluations. It is noteworthy that many unusual experience factors, compared to conventional planning, rated high in both negative and positive evaluations of perceived value of travel time such as ‘Ability to do what I

wanted', 'Scenery' or 'Other people'. Regarding the correlation among **worthwhileness and experience factors**, it was found a higher frequency of trip legs with positive experience factors for higher values of worthwhileness. The analysis of worthwhileness ratings in relation to the **combination of experience factors and activities** demonstrated that different activities were carried out when value of travel time was rated high or low with different experience factors selected as well.

The analysis demonstrated that approximately 40% of the trip legs where **reliability** had a positive impact were given the best evaluation in terms of worthwhileness. This indicates that reliability can play an important role in a positive travel experience. When comparing reliability across trip purposes, this is more frequently reported as a positive factor for the maximum worthwhileness value of 5 in 'Leisure' or 'Everyday Shopping' trips compared to trips to 'Work' or 'Home'.

The data analysis performed among the two **genders** has revealed interesting findings. Female users were reporting fewer negative factors when the trip was more worthwhile (for ratings 3 to 5) while this relation was opposite for male users. Furthermore, it was shown that male users present higher worthwhileness values in all experience factors related to smoothness apart from the "Vehicle ride smoothness". Crowdedness and seating availability experience factor is more important for high speed and intercity train trip legs among male users of the app rather than long bus journeys which remains the first mode for female users. Regarding the analysis of activities, Thinking activity together with Cycling were the ones with the most notable difference between male and female users.

Looking at different modes of transport, **cycling and walking** trip legs were rated higher in terms of their worthwhileness compared to other mode categories, both when positive or negative experience factors were selected by users. Furthermore, when smoothness factors were selected for active modes, the trip legs received higher worthwhileness ratings. In particular, when factors related to smoothness of travel were negatively rated, Cycling and Personal Care activities were selected more frequently while Accompanying someone and Relaxing or sleeping were less reported, indicating that these factors correlate with activities in a different way.

Public transport modes as well as **private motorised modes** were found to be more sensitivity to reliability of travel time. Crowdedness and seating availability experience factor was mostly reported to have a positive impact on the value of travel time and it was among the top 5 experience factors most frequently selected in trip legs performed by **public transport modes**. Travellers tend to give more importance to "Crowdedness_Seating" when journeys with public transport are longer, with long distance bus, high speed and intercity train trip legs presenting higher relative counts.

When filtering trip legs by alternative modes performed by **users of private motorised modes**, the importance of experience factors is quite different to the average trend. These findings can provide insights towards which are the areas of improvement that can lead to increased levels of satisfaction for trips within Cycling & Emerging Micromobility and Public Transport Short Distance potentially shifting car drivers travel behaviour.

6. Discussion and future work

This section presents a discussion on the approach, potential future work and next steps to be followed.

The data analysis presented in this report has revealed a variety of different attributes that travellers perceive as important when evaluating their travel time. The 'Ability to do what I wanted', the 'Scenery' or 'Other people' were selected among the most frequent experience factors reported by users of the app, demonstrating that travellers perspective differs significantly compared to the approach of conventional planning where time and cost are the main players of time savings. Investigating such qualitative aspects of the value of travel time can improve travel experience and guide policies towards shaping more sustainable travel patterns.

Additional analysis of the travel data collected from the Woorti app could potentially reveal more correlations between the variables influencing the value of travel time. The planned scientific publications to be submitted within the scope of the MoTiV project as well as *Deliverable 5.1* on Cost Benefit Analysis and the Worthwhileness Index will shed light on further results. Furthermore, the forthcoming *Deliverable 6.5* will provide guidelines on Policies and Business Recommendations addressing among others the impact of MoTiV findings on VTT with important implications for urban and transport planners, policy makers and public authorities.

The concept of worthwhileness is complex with many variables and different interrelations among them. The perception of travellers on the value of travel time depends on different variables ranging from experience factors, traveller equipment and travel activities to travellers characteristics and attitudes, trip characteristics or spatial and temporal attributes. Considering the multi-dimensionality of worthwhile or wasted travel time as perceived by travellers, it is challenging to identify and demonstrate the importance of factors influencing this perception with confidence. The qualitative character of many of these variables adds more to this complexity.

Therefore, the complexity of this concept requires a more detailed analysis and data modelling which can potentially identify additional correlations. A few examples of additional analysis can focus on exploring the importance of experience factors across different countries, the difference of modal choice in various countries, the weight that different experience factors or activities have on worthwhileness ratings and the differences in gender, age groups or socioeconomic status. Additional research could also focus on the reasons behind the selection of specific experience factors such as the 'Ability to do what I wanted'. Towards shaping more sustainable travel patterns, factors hindering the wider adoption of cycling can be further explored, for example factors related to lack of safe infrastructure.

In terms of the data collection method, the design and formulation of the questions may have introduced bias in terms of how respondents interpreted the questions asked. The first question asked to users of the app on "Overall, how did you feel about this trip?" with a rating from Lousy (1 star) to Great (5 stars) mostly received responses between 3 and 5. The same concentration of responses was also observed for the trip leg validation question on "Was your travel time wasted or worthwhile" with a 5-star rating response system receiving again most of the responses between 3 and 5. A possible cause of this pattern could be the 5-star rating system which only offers 5 possible responses. Users of the app may have felt that assigning a value of 1 or 2 stars to these questions is too extreme. A more detailed focus and assessment of responses between the values 3 and 5 could reveal additional findings. Another potential bias may have been introduced by specific attributes of users (e.g. cyclists

or specific age groups) that were engaged in the data collection campaigns as described in *Deliverable 4.3*.

At the same time, the data collection method via the Woorti app enabled a wider collection of data across different countries into a single database, in comparison to other data collection methods such as questionnaires or interviews. The use of the app allowed for a wide coverage of diverse population excluding however those with no access to smart phones. Nevertheless, the coverage of different characteristics of the population is quite diverse as shown in the demographic statistics presented at Figure 1 in [Section 4.3](#).

The findings of the data analysis presented in this report can provide the basis for further research revealing at the same time the areas of improvement in terms of the methodology and tools used. Overall, and perhaps more importantly, the MoTiV results presented in this report make the case that from a traveller perspective, the experience of travel time matters which can place the user experience in a central role in transport planning. The findings of this report bring important insights for conventional transport planning and assessment tools that are currently based on more simplified set of variables such as travel costs and absolute time savings on mode-specific portions of door-to-door trips. Furthermore, this report provides important implications for urban and transport planners, policy makers and authorities to update the current assessment methodology for transport projects, contributing to a gender-sensitive and inclusive design of future mobility services and transport infrastructure (e.g. Mobility as a Service, Connected and Automated Driving). Ultimately, this knowledge is expected to support inclusive transport policies balancing the 'need for speed' and 'accessibility' with investments that increase the perceived quality of travel time, increasing individuals' well-being and ensuring integration of all different groups of the population in the society, aiming at closing the existing equity gap.

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8. Appendices

Appendix 1: Weather scenarios – variables and categories

Clouds	Description	Category
None	no clouds	Clear sky
Clear	clear sky	
	few clouds	Partially cloudy
	scattered clouds	
	broken clouds	
Clouds	overcast clouds	Sky completely cloudy

Table 22: Categories and description of intensity of clouds

Precipitation	Description	Category
None	no precipitation	Light
Rain	light rain	
	moderate rain	Moderate
	heavy intensity rain	Heavy
Snow	light snow	Light
	snow	Heavy

Table 23: Categories and description of precipitation levels

Beaufort scale	Short Description	Wind speed	Description	Category
0	Calm	< 0.5 m/s	Calm. Smoke rises vertically.	Light breeze (From calm to light leaves motion)
1	Light air	0.5–1.5 m/s	Wind motion visible in smoke.	
2	Light breeze	1.6–3.3 m/s	Wind felt on exposed skin. Leaves rustle.	
3	Gentle breeze	3.4–5.5 m/s	Leaves and smaller twigs in constant motion.	Strong breeze (Things start to move)
4	Moderate breeze	5.5–7.9 m/s	Dust and loose paper raised. Small branches begin to move.	
5	Fresh breeze	8–10.7 m/s	Branches of a moderate size move. Small trees begin to sway.	
6	Strong breeze	10.8–13.8 m/s	Large branches in motion. Whistling heard in overhead wires. Umbrella use becomes difficult. Empty plastic garbage cans tip over.	
7	High wind	13.9–17.1 m/s	Whole trees in motion. Effort needed to walk against the wind. Swaying of skyscrapers may be felt, especially by people on upper floors.	Gale (Wind causes damage)
8	Gale	17.2–20.7 m/s	Twigs broken from trees. Cars veer on road.	
9	Strong/severe gale	20.8–24.4 m/s	Larger branches break off trees, and some small trees blow over.	
			Construction/temporary signs and barricades blow over. Damage to circus tents and canopies.	
10	Storm	24.5–28.4 m/s	Trees are broken off or uprooted, saplings bent and deformed, poorly attached asphalt shingles and shingles in poor condition peel off roofs.	
11	Violent storm	28.5–32.6 m/s	Widespread vegetation damage. More damage to most roofing surfaces, asphalt tiles	

			that have curled up and/or fractured due to age may break away completely.
12	Hurricane force	$\geq 32,6$ m/s	Considerable and widespread damage to vegetation, a few windows broken, structural damage to mobile homes and poorly constructed sheds and barns. Debris may be hurled about.

Table 24: Categories, description and Beaufort scale of wind speeds

Celsius degrees	Category
< 0	Uncomfortably Cold
0-15	Cool
15-25	Comfortable
25-32	Warm
>32	Uncomfortably Hot

Table 25: Celsius degrees and categories of apparent temperature

Appendix 2: Additional results on Hypothesis 15 – Question 14

Figure 49: Distribution of absolute counts of trip legs performed by Walking modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 50: Distribution of absolute counts of trip legs performed by Cycling & Emerging Micromobility modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 51: Distribution of absolute counts of trip legs performed by Public Transport Short Distance modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 52: Distribution of absolute counts of trip legs performed by Public Transport Long Distance modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Figure 53: Distribution of absolute counts of trip legs performed by Private Motorised modes across worthwhileness ratings in different weather scenarios

Appendix 3: Additional results on Hypothesis 1 – Question 1

Figure 54: Box plots illustrating the median, lower and upper quartiles of mood scoring across different number of legs within a trip for all countries

Figure 55: Box plots illustrating the median, lower and upper quartiles of mood scoring across different number of legs within a trip for different age groups

Appendix 4: Additional results on Hypothesis 2 – Question 1

Figure 56: Reliability as a positive and negative factor across different worthwhileness values by country

Figure 57: Reliability as a positive and negative factor across different worthwhileness values on a weekday and weekend

Appendix 5: Additional results on Hypothesis 15 – Question 1

Walking	Number of trip legs	Cycling & Emerging Micromobility	Number of trip legs
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	6484	Todays_Weather	4265
Todays_Weather	5490	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	4155
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	4571	Road_Path_Directness	2948
Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	4233	Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	2804
Road_Path_Quality	3337	Road_Path_Quality	2555
Road_Path_Directness	3139	Scenery	2342
Scenery	2997	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	2309
Other_People	2525	Parking_At_End_Points	1743
Air_Quality	2163	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	1429
Lighting_Visibility	2041	Lighting_Visibility	1393
PT long distance	Number of trip legs	PT short distance	Number of trip legs
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	181	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	2396
Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	160	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	2064
Scenery	138	Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	1768
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	132	Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	1600
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	126	Security_And_Safety	1518
Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	124	Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	1393
Crowdedness_Seating	123	Crowdedness_Seating	1381
Security_And_Safety	119	Payment_And_Tickets	1319
Todays_Weather	103	Scenery	1260
Payment_And_Tickets	100	Todays_Weather	1073
Private Motorised	Number of trip legs		
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	5339		
Vehicle_Quality	3741		
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	3689		
Todays_Weather	3671		
Parking_At_End_Points	3437		
Other_Passengers	3328		
Road_Quality_Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	3116		
Seat_Comfort	3105		
Scenery	3043		
Security_And_Safety	2849		

Table 26: Top 10 experience factors that contributed positively to the perceived value of travel time across transport mode categories

Walking	Number of trip legs	Cycling & Emerging Micromobility	Number of trip legs
Noise_Level	1089	Cars_Other_Vehicles	2230
Cars_Other_Vehicles	1050	Air_Quality	1606
Air_Quality	1046	Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	1457
Todays_Weather	927	Noise_Level	1421
Road_Path_Quality	691	Road_Path_Quality	1222
Crowding_Congestion	682	Traffic_Signals_Crossings	1075

Facilities_Shower_Lockers	594	Crowding_Congestion	1055
Scenery	521	Todays_Weather	734
Traffic_Signals_Crossings	484	Facilities_Shower_Lockers	537
Road_Path_Availability_And_Safety	483	Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	510
PT long distance	Number of trip legs	PT short distance	Number of trip legs
Internet_Connectivity	54	Privacy	653
Privacy	52	Other_People	623
Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	46	Crowdedness_Seating	622
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	44	Noise_Level	594
Noise_Level	38	Seating_Quality_Personal_Space	580
Other_People	37	Charging_Opportunity	521
Crowdedness_Seating	36	Internet_Connectivity	504
Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	35	Air_Quality	481
Food_Drink_Available	33	Scenery	463
Todays_Weather	33	Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	377
Private Motorised	Number of trip legs		
Traffic_Congestion_Delays	1604		
Other_Cars_Vehicles	911		
Todays_Weather	884		
Ability_To_Do_What_I_Wanted	797		
Scenery	760		
Road_Quality_Vehicle_Ride_Smoothness	606		
Reliability_Of_Travel_Time	523		
Parking_At_End_Points	508		
Simplicity_Difficulty_Of_The_Route	506		
Charging_Opportunity	402		

Table 27: Top 10 experience factors that contributed negatively to the perceived value of travel time across transport mode categories